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Work Package WP5

Open and secure ICT for modular resilient optimized hybrid grid

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Hybrid AC/DC data model for interoperability

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List of Abbreviations

OWL	Web Ontology Language
HADGO	Hybrid Ac Dc Grid Ontology
AC	Alternating Current
API	Application Programming Interface
BEMS	Building Energy Management Systems
BFO	Basic Formal Ontology
CIs	Critical Infrastructures
CIM	Common Information Model
DABGEO	Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology
DBMS	Database management system
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DFD	Data Flow Diagram
DL	Description Logic
DoA	Description of Action
DR	Demand Response
DSOs	Distribution System Operators
DTDL	Digital Twins Definition Language
EDI	Electronic Data Interchange
EIP	Eco-Industrial Park
EMs	Energy Management Systems
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GWAC	GridWise Architecture Council
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air-Conditioning
IAO	Information Artifact Ontology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device
IoT	Internet of Things
IRIs	Internationalized Resource Identifiers
IT	Information Technology
IUDX	India Urban Data Exchange
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LOV	Linked Open Vocabularies
LVDC	Low Voltage Direct Current
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
NGSI	Next Generation Service Interface
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interface Linked Data
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NOCT	Normal Operating Cell Temperature
OASC	Open and Agile Smart Cities
OEMA	Ontology for Energy Management Applications
OEO	Open Energy Ontology
OEP	Open Energy Platform
OSI	Open Systems Interconnect
OWL	Web Ontology Language
OWL-DL	Web Ontology Language Description Logic
PEP	Process Execution Platform
PID	Proportional-Integral-Derivative

PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PMUs	Phasor Measurement Units
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RO	Relations Ontology
SAREF	Smart Appliances REference
SARGON	SmArt eneRGy dOmain oNtology
SG-CG	Smart Grids Coordination Group
SEAS	Smart Energy Aware Systems
SG	Smart Grid
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management Systems
SSN	Semantic Sensor Network
STC	Standard Test Condition
UML	Unified Modeling Language
UNA	Unique Name Assumption
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
VPPs	Virtual Power Plants
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XSD	XML Schema Definition
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

The role of Distributed Energy Resources (DER) is increasing significantly in electrical power systems due to many environmental, economic, and political drivers. This transition has also put the electrical distribution grid in a central role. The challenges arising from this transition are largely being addressed under Smart Grid (SG) initiatives.

Although there is no standard definition, in general, a SG refers to a method of incorporating intelligence into the operation of a distribution grid to increase flexibility and performance. For electrical power systems, Alternating Current (AC) distribution grids are a well-known infrastructure that has been in use for a long time. This infrastructure can be assisted by Direct Current (DC) technologies as a possible backbone to increase, for example, Renewable Energy Sources (RES) hosting capacity; however, they must be designed on a solid basis to allow for rapid roll-out and integration. It is critical to provide and test suitable methodologies and resources to lower entry barriers for early adoption processes to maximize the implementation capability of new DC technologies.

The HYPERRIDE project aims to support this transition toward the transformation in the electrical grid infrastructure by laying the groundwork for widespread adoption of DC technology. The future distribution grid both at the Low Voltage Direct Current (LVDC) component to Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC) backbone is planned to be demonstrated at three pilot sites (Germany, Italy, and Switzerland) implementing relevant use cases. These pilots will provide valuable insights and help identify the gaps in knowledge and possible solutions for the various focus areas. The use cases for the implementation are documented in this deliverable along with the standards and background, the methodology, and the analysis.

Interoperability among the components and sub-systems of the developed AC/DC hybrid power system solution is a key goal in the HYPERRIDE project, as having an interoperable solution has numerous benefits for all stakeholders. In general, interoperability implies that information conveyed from a sender system to a receiver system can be used meaningfully by the latter, necessitating at least some interpretation and contextualization of the data. One of the main goals of the HYPERRIDE project is to achieve a higher level of interoperability.

Interoperability is a challenging quality attribute to achieve because it necessitates a thorough understanding of the problem, the solution, and its interrelation. Data is at the center of interoperability, necessitating its consideration in any effort to achieve a higher level of interoperability.

In most circumstances, data interoperability is a challenge to be addressed when two systems are unable to communicate because the information they share is either encoded differently or using a different data structure. This points out that interoperability is concerned with how the two communicating systems use some data model that is abstracted and updated to meet the needs of the two systems. An ontology is a formal description of knowledge as a set of concepts within a domain and their interrelationships and provides an abstract model that can describe, in a formal language based on mathematical logic, relevant aspects (concepts, relationships, properties, facts, rules) of a phenomenon or domain of interest that is intended to be represented for some purpose. Apart from being useful for many other aspects, an ontology provides a sound basis for developing an interoperable data model. Development of an ontology for AC/DC hybrid power system is the goal of this task. This deliverable reports the background, motivation, state-of-the-art, development methodology, and description of the ontology itself.

Developing data models in a heterogeneous and uncoordinated manner typically results in *data*

stovepipes/data silo issues, which can be challenging for attaining interoperability and impede the ontology's reusability potential while also making integration difficult. Ontological realism is a method of developing an ontology to be more like a reality model than a data model in order to maximize its utility and stability. It is being advocated as one of the best practices for ontology development and is used to create models for most of the data sources in the world. HADGO is being developed using the ontological realism technique based on basic hybrid AC/DC grid models in conjunction with expert knowledge, judgments, and opinions from the involved experts.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

According to the Description of Action (DoA) (*HYPERRIDE Description of Action*, 2020), this report will focus on *defining a data model to ensure interoperability in the hybrid AC/DC grids*.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 provides information about the report content. Next, Section 2 provides some background and motivation for developing an interoperable data model and ontology. This section provides a short explanation of some important concepts like interoperability, ontology, and data modeling. Then in Section 3 is provided a detailed analysis of the current state-of-the-art in data models, ontologies, and vocabularies, with a particular focus on power system design operation and analysis; it is organized into two categories: *Data Models*, *Open Ontologies and Vocabularies*.

Figure 1: Structure of the deliverable document.

This task is dealing with developing an interoperable data model for hybrid AC/DC electrical power systems. However, any such attempt would be too challenging without having a well-defined methodology that should help in understanding the problem, the solution, and their interrelationship. Section 4 then describes one such methodology that has been developed for the development of an ontology and the interoperable data model. The developed Hybrid AC DC Grid Ontology (HADGO) is introduced in Section 5. The deliverable is concluded in

Section 6. Appendix A provides some more details about the HADGO by providing axioms on the entity classes and providing a reference to various data and object properties.

2 Background and Motivation

The evolution of computer systems moved from single monolithic systems capable to solve a precise problem, to highly distributed systems of systems that in many cases connect widely available systems deployed across the Internet with extremely localized ubiquitous systems such as sensor networks or networks of actuators. Flexible and efficient automation systems and industrial processes are implemented by integrating computational systems and physical processes, thereby forming large heterogeneous systems of cyber-physical systems¹. In order to enable the heterogeneity among systems of systems, different levels of interoperability need to be enabled.

2.1 Interoperability

In the IEEE Standard Glossary of Software Engineering Terminology (“IEEE Standard Glossary of Software Engineering Terminology”, 1990), interoperability has been defined as *“the ability of two or more systems or components to exchange information and to use the information that has been exchanged”*. Therefore, the concept of interoperability goes beyond the simple transfer of information, which is mainly covered by the Open Systems Interconnect (OSI) model (ITU-T, 1994). Interoperability also implies that the information transferred by sender system to a receiver system can be used in some meaningful way by the latter and this requires at least some interpretation and contextualization of the data. In most cases, the problem of data interoperation arises when two systems are not able to interoperate because the two systems encode the information they share in two different data structures. The problem of data format mismatch is just the easiest form of data interoperability, since it assumes that the semantics of the messages that the systems exchange is equivalent. Actually, there are many conditions in which this assumption is not true, for example when the information expected by one system is different from the information provided by the other one. Hence, the interoperability is related to how the two systems use the same information and how the information is abstracted and modified to satisfy the requirements of the two systems.

Data interoperability has been widely addressed by standardisation activities with efforts such as Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) (Narayanan, Maruchek, & Handfield, 2009). The problem is that standardization alone is too weak, slow and expensive to address the problem. Moreover, data interoperability has been also widely studied by the Data-Base community in terms of integrating data from different databases very quickly and efficiently (Haas, Lin, & Roth, 2002). The lesson learnt from databases is that systems of systems need to be able to recognize automatically the information that is encoded in the different types of data and then reason about the different encoding to derive a mapping between data structures. Therefore, what is needed to address the problem of data interoperability is to model the meaning of the messages that systems exchange, so that data mappings can be derived automatically at the level of the meaning of the data, rather than at the level of the data format (Paolucci & Souville, 2012).

2.2 Ontology

The domain knowledge represented by “ontologies” is being widely used in the design process of information systems. An ontology is a formal description of knowledge as a set of concepts

¹<http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1357311/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

within a domain and the relationships that hold between them (Lauretis, Costantini, & Letteri, 2019). An ontology is, hence, an *abstract and simplified model* that describes, through the use of a *formal language* based on mathematical logic, relevant aspects (concepts, relationships, properties, facts, rules) of a *phenomenon or domain of interest* that is intended to be represented for *some purpose*. Since terms and relations are shared by the entire community of the domain of interest, there is no ambiguity: an ontology describes a specific knowledge in an unambiguous way.

Relationships between concepts enable automated reasoning on data, easy to implement in semantic graph databases that use ontologies as their semantic schema. Ontologies work and reason with concepts and relationships in ways that are very similar to the way humans perceive interlinked concepts. Another relevant feature of the ontologies is that they are easy to extend since relationships and concept matching can be easily added to existing ontologies. As a result, ontologies can evolve with the growth of data without impacting dependent processes and systems. Furthermore, ontologies allow to represent any format of data (including unstructured, semi-structured, or structured data) enabling easier data integration, concept and text mining, and data-driven analytics.

Each piece of information will be mapped by its own ontology and can be inserted in a context that relates it to other ontologies, so as to create logical relationships that allow, for example, to distinguish the meaning of the word "tree" in a context of "natural environment" from "tree" in a context of "navigation". Thanks to this approach, it is possible to imagine that each piece of information will have a complete meaning in a certain context, according to the mechanism of association of information typical of the human mind.

The semantic structuring that can be achieved using ontologies differs from the more superficial composition and formatting of information managed, for example, by relational databases or semi-structured storage systems, such as Extensible Markup Language (XML) data bases. With databases, the entire semantic content must be virtually captured in the application logic; in practice, the program that uses the database as a source of information should have a method for categorizing the information semantically. Ontologies provide an objective specification of a given domain that represents a shared view of the concepts and relationships that characterise the domain knowledge. In other words, it is possible to separate the representation of the domain from the logic of its elaboration. There are different levels of ontologies:

- Upper Domain Ontology, where general concepts common to multiple application domains, abstract concepts, philosophical level concepts, and reusable concepts are placed;
- Application Ontology, where specific concepts (but not elementary) of the individual applications that characterize a specific domain are placed;
- Lower Domain Ontology, where elementary concepts that cannot be further refined or decomposed are placed.

An ontology is composed of:

- classes (general concepts of the domain of interest);
- relations between these classes;
- properties assigned to each concept, which describe various types of its attributes;
- restrictions on properties that impose the type of data on the value that the property can take.

Figure 2: Level of complexity in semantic representation

As of the classes of the ontology, it is possible to define instances, which represent specific objects of the real-world that inherit attributes and relationships from the classes. The ontology and the set of class instances constitute the knowledge base.

The classes of an ontology can be in relationship of inheritance with other classes, forming a so-called taxonomy. A taxonomy just a hierarchical structure of terms that represent the relationships and attributes among those terms. It is only a classification system of how terms relate, and other information is needed to establish the meaning and usages of those terms. In essence, a taxonomy is a subpart of an ontology, which contains the information and properties about the terms classified in the taxonomy. A taxonomy is typically a controlled vocabulary in which all the terms belong to a single hierarchical structure and have parent/child relationships to other terms. A well-established taxonomy is the imperative first step in defining an ontology to promote interoperability.

As shown in Figure 2, the type of semantic representation determines the level of meaning captured within the representation. A vocabulary is a list of terms within a specific domain. A taxonomy is a controlled vocabulary with hierarchical *is-A* relationships that express inheritance between classes by creating a hierarchy (first level, second level, etc.). An ontology is a taxonomy with additional relationships, such as *has part*. The information provided by these relationships is necessary for developing atlases that link together data across space and time.

Classes are called primitive, if there are no other classes from which they have been derived, or defined, if they have been inherited from other classes in the ontology (Costin, Eastman, & Issa, 2017).

Taxonomies and ontologies contain formal assertions and constraints, called axioms, that represent the rules for how the terms, properties, and attributes are related and are used. Axioms are an important part of developing a taxonomy and ontology because they provide truths and assumptions that give meaning to the terminology.

In order to have a shared interpretation of reality, allowing not only people but also software to establish logical links between the information contents of a domain, it is necessary to make explicit in a formal way concepts and relations of the knowledge domain one intends to represent. To be useful, ontologies must therefore be expressed in a concrete notation, i.e., they need a formally defined language. The languages that by their nature lend themselves to the definition of ontologies are: XML, Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Web Ontology Language (OWL).

2.2.1 XML

XML is an extensible markup language that allows the creation of customised tags, the basic elements of a syntactic mechanism that allows the definition and control of the meaning of elements contained in a document or text (W3C, 2008). An XML document is characterised by components, called elements, organised according to a hierarchical structure, with a main element, called root element or, simply, root. Each element represents a logical component of the document and may contain other elements (sub-elements) or text. Elements may be associated with other information (attributes) that describe their properties. XML schemas, on the other hand, are documents used to define and validate the content and structure of XML data, in the same way that a database schema defines and validates the tables, columns, and data types that make up a database. An XML schema allows to define and describe certain types of XML data, using the XML Schema Definition (XSD) language usually. XSD defines the type of an XML document in terms of constraints; it defines which elements and attributes can appear, in what relationship to each other, what type of data it can contain, and more. It can also be used with a validation programme, in order to ascertain which type a given XML document belongs to.

2.2.2 RDF (Resource Description Framework)

RDF is a standard proposed by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) (W3C, 2014) that provides a framework for encoding, exchanging and reusing structured metadata. RDF allows describing resources and the relationships between resources, where the term resource means anything (a person, a web page, a document) that can be uniquely identified through a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI). RDF introduces a formalism for the representation of metadata based on the concept of statements encoded in: subject (the resource), predicate (the property, attribute, or characteristic of the resource), object (the value of the property/attribute/characteristic). The idea is to use a data structure organised according to an oriented graph, where resources are represented as nodes (graphically ellipses), properties as labelled oriented arcs, and the corresponding values as rectangles. In order to uniquely identify properties RDF adopts the mechanism of namespaces. XML namespaces provide a way to unambiguously identify the semantics and conventions governing the use of properties by identifying the authority that manages the vocabulary. RDF is an abstract description model and places no constraints on the syntax and meaning of resource description. However, for practical reasons, the W3C has proposed the use of XML as the language for representing the RDF model (W3C, 2004b). RDF only allows to describe the properties of an object, without defining any level of hierarchy or relationship between classes. This is, instead, the task of RDF Schema, XML structures based on RDF concepts that facilitate the creation of links between objects. Statements may be represented by means of the XML syntax or by means of the 'Turtle' or 'N3' syntaxes, the latter being an abbreviation of the XML syntax.

2.2.3 OWL (Web Ontology Language)

OWL defined by W3C in 2004 (W3C, 2004a), is a language to explicitly represent meaning and semantics of terms with vocabularies and relations between them. The description of a concept is done by recursively composing logical constructs that allow to define a concept as the intersection, union, complement, disjunction, or enumeration of several concepts. In OWL, entities are identified by Internationalized Resource Identifiers (IRIs), but unlike some approaches, OWL does not adopt the Unique Name Assumption (UNA). Thus, in OWL different IRIs can be

assigned to the same entity. OWL provides the predicate SameAs to indicate when two different IRIs denote the same entity. The goal of OWL is not only to allow the attribution of meanings to resources (reusing some RDF constructs), but also to make these meanings computable, i.e., to allow automatic mechanisms (in particular computers or computer networks) to evaluate inferences about these meanings.

2.3 Data model

Unlike ontologies, which represent agreed domain semantics and whose fundamental asset is their relative independence of particular applications (i.e., an ontology consists of relatively generic knowledge that can be reused by different kinds of applications/tasks), data models, such as database or XML-schemes, represent the structure and integrity of the data elements of the, in principle “single”, specific enterprise application(s) by which it will be used. Hence, the conceptualisation and the vocabulary related to a data model are not intended a priori to be shared by other applications; building data models usually depends on the specific needs and tasks that have to be performed within this enterprise. The semantics of data models often constitute an informal agreement between the developers and the users of the data model. Both ontologies and data models must consider the structure and the rules of the domain to model; but, while data models are task-specific and implementation-oriented, ontologies, by definition, should be as much generic and task-independent as possible. The more an ontology approximates the ideal of being a formal, agreed and shared resource, the more shareable and reusable it becomes (Spyns, Meersman, & Jarrar, 2002).

A data model can be sometimes referred to as a data structure, especially in the context of programming languages. A data model organises data elements and standardises how those elements relate to one another. Data models are often used to facilitate the communication between the business people defining the requirements for a computer system and the technical people defining the design in response to those requirements. They are used to show the data needed and created by business processes and are specified in a data modelling notation, which is often graphical in form. The following models can be used to represent a data model (Wikipedia, n.d.):

- A **Data Flow Diagram (DFD)** is a graphical or visual representation using a standardised set of symbols and notations to describe a business’s operations through data movement. DFD allows to depict the business requirements of applications by representing the sequence of process steps and flow of information using a graphical representation or visual representation rather than a textual description. When used through an entire development process, they first document the results of business analysis. Then, they refine the representation to show how information moves through, and is changed by, application flows. Both automated and manual processes are represented.
- An **Object Model** is a collection of objects or classes through which a program can examine and manipulate some specific parts of its world. In other words, the object-oriented interface to some service or system. Such an interface is said to be the object model of the represented service or system. The basic factors of an object model are classes and objects. An object is a physical component in the object-oriented domain and may be tangible such as a person, car, or intangible such as a project. A class is a representation of objects. It represents a group of objects that have similar properties and exhibit an expected behavior.
- **Object-Role Modeling** is a fact-oriented method for performing systems analysis at the

conceptual level. The quality of a database application depends on its design critically. To help ensure correctness, clarity, adaptability and productivity, information systems are best specified first at the conceptual level, using concepts and language that people can readily understand. The conceptual design may include data, process and behavioral perspectives, and the actual Database management system (DBMS) used to implement the design might be based on one of many logical data models (relational, hierarchic, network, object-oriented etc.).

- An **Information model** is not exactly a type of data model, but more or less an alternative model. Within the field of software engineering both a data model and an information model can be abstract, formal representations of entity types that include their properties, relationships, and the operations that can be performed on them. The entity types in the model may be kinds of real-world objects, such as devices in a network, or they may themselves be abstract, such as for the entities used in a billing system. Typically, they are used to model a constrained domain that can be described by a closed set of entity types, properties, relationships and operations. An information model provides formalism to the description of a problem domain without constraining how that description is mapped to an actual implementation in software. There may be many mappings of the information model. Such mappings are called data models, irrespective of whether they are object models (e.g., using Unified Modeling Language (UML)), entity relationship models or XML schemas.

3 State of the Art

Conducting a state-of-the-art analysis is critical because it provides valuable insight into the problem domain by revealing trends, methodologies, and technology. During the course of this work, extensive analysis was carried out. This aids in the latter development phase of this work when a new ontology for a hybrid AC/DC system will be built, in locating relevant and/or similar concepts. This section summarizes the state-of-the-art in data models, ontologies, and vocabularies for power system design and analysis. The analysis is organized into two categories: *Data Models, Open Ontologies and Vocabularies* as shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: State of the Art Organization

3.1 Data Models

Data Models play a crucial role in interoperability because they provide harmonized representation formats and semantics that will be used by applications both to consume and publish data. In the following sections, an overview of data models relevant for the HYPERRIDE project is presented.

3.1.1 Smart Data Models

Smart Data Models² is a program led by FIWARE, India Urban Data Exchange (IUDX), TM Forum, Open and Agile Smart Cities (OASC), and others to support the adoption of a reference architecture and compatible common data models as the basis of a digital market of interoperable and replicable smart solutions in multiple sectors, starting with smart cities. The reference architecture and data models use the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), Next Generation Service Interface (NGSI), Application Programming Interface (API), (GS, 2020) and TM Forum Open APIs³ for interoperability and scalability solutions, thus providing the foundation for breaking information silos in organisations and allow organisations to become smart. The common definition of smart data models empowers companies to develop solutions that adhere to this common definition and ultimately help enable the interoperability of services.

FIWARE data models have been harmonized to enable data portability for different application domains including Smart Cities, Smart Agrifood, Smart Environment, Smart Sensing, Smart Energy, Smart Water, and other domains. Following an open standard contribution approach, and to guarantee maximum adoption, FIWARE Data models are stored in GitHub dedicated repositories⁴. The lower-level repository is a Subject (for example, Alert, Weather, etc). Every subject repository is aggregated into Domain repositories (for example, Smart Cities and in Smart Environment). At the same time, a subject could appear in several domains (for example, the subject Weather appears in Smart Cities and in Smart Environment).

Even though data models have been designed to be compliant with FIWARE NGSI version 2 and Next Generation Service Interface Linked Data (NGSI-LD)⁵, the data models are intended to be used wherever possible. FIWARE continuously seeks contributors to existing data models for new ones. Below domains relevant to the HYPERRIDE project are described.

Smart Energy domain⁶ compiles subjects related with:

- Battery;
- Energy;
- EnergyCIM;
- GreenEnergy.

The Battery subject comprises the following entity types:

- Battery, which represents a physical battery with its hardware specifications;

²<https://smartdatamodels.org/index.php/list-of-data-models-3/>

³<https://www.tmforum.org/open-apis/>

⁴<https://github.com/smart-data-models>

⁵<https://github.com/FIWARE/specifications>

⁶<https://github.com/smart-data-models/SmartEnergy>

- BatteryStatus, which represents the status for a physical battery;
- StorageBatteryDevice, which describes the technical characteristics of the battery and the charging and discharging conditions of the energy;
- StorageBatteryMeasurement, which measures the remaining energy capacity in a battery.

The Energy subject comprises the following entity types:

- ACMeasurement, which is intended to measure the electrical energies consumed by an electrical system that uses an AC for a three-phase (L1, L2, L3) or single-phase (L) and neutral (N). It includes attributes for various electrical measurements such as power, frequency, current and voltage;
- InverterDevice, which describes the mechanical, electrical characteristics of an Inverter according to DC - Direct Current Information supplied as input and AC - Alternating Current Information returned as output;
- SolarEnergy, which is a data model for Solar Energy generation;
- TechnicalCabinetDevice, which describes the technical characteristics of the Device, designed to be placed in an urban or interurban environment. The main objective of these cabinets for this Data Model is to protect the electrical equipment necessary for the control, surveillance, reading and management of urban lighting, signaling, video and electrical distribution;
- ThreePhaseAcMeasurement, which represents the electrical measurement from a system that uses three-phase alternating current.

The EnergyCIM subject comprises entity types adapted from IEC CIM data models. As an example, *PowerTransformer data model represents an electrical device consisting of two or more coupled windings, with or without a magnetic core, for introducing mutual coupling between electric circuits. Transformers can be used to control voltage and phase shift (active power flow). A power transformer may be composed of separate transformer tanks that need not be identical. A power transformer can be modeled with or without tanks and is intended for use in both balanced and unbalanced representations. A power transformer typically has two terminals but may have one (grounding), or three or more terminals.*

The GreenEnergy subject comprises the following entity types:

- GreenEnergyGenerator, which represents a generic generator station that can generate energy from green energy;
- GreenEnergyMeasurement, which represents an instantaneous measure of power generation using green energy sources;
- PhotovoltaicDevice, which describes the mechanical, electrical, and thermal characteristics of photo-voltaic panels according to Standard Test Condition (STC) and Normal Operating Cell Temperature (NOCT);
- PhotovoltaicMeasurement, which is intended to measure the continuous power transferred by the photo-voltaic panel to an Inverter Device.

The Smart-Sensing domain compiles the subjects of the Device. The following entity types are available:

- Camera, which represents a camera installation in a city;

- Device, which represents an apparatus (hardware + software + firmware) intended to accomplish a particular task (sensing the environment, actuating, etc.);
- DeviceMeasurement, which is intended to represent a generic measurement entity coming from a device or other data source;
- DeviceModel, which captures the static properties of a device;
- DeviceOperation, which contains a harmonised description of a generic device operation entity that contains dynamic data reported by a device and is therefore applicable to all Internet of Things (IoT) segments and related IoT applications;
- PrivacyObject, which provides information about privacy for an IoT device;
- SmartMeteringObservation, which contains a harmonised description of a Smart Meter Observation.

3.1.2 Common Information Model (CIM)

The smartness of a power grid is strictly linked to the ability to respond to dynamic changes in both supply and demand while providing reliable service and maintaining an optimum economy. This would not be possible without a high degree of interoperability between its systems and their components.

Figure 4: GWAC Stack (Widergren et al., 2008).

The GridWise Architecture Council (GWAC) Stack (Widergren et al., 2008) has been adopted by both the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and the Smart Grids Coordination Group (SG-CG), as an interoperability reference framework between the different domains and actors in their models, respectively the NIST Conceptual Architectural Framework (Gopstein, Nguyen, and N. Hastings, & Wollman, 2021) and the EU SG-CG Smart Grid Reference Architecture (Bruinenberg et al., 2012). By being integrated into the dominant conceptual reference architectures, this interoperability framework has become fundamental to the conceptualization of SG interoperability. In its conceptualization of end-to-end interoperability,

the GWAC Stack is structured in eight levels (Figure 4) ranging from “Basic Connectivity” at the physical level of component interoperability to “Economic/Regulatory Policy” at the organizational level, where Business Objectives and Procedures take place. The term “end-to-end” interoperability is to describe effective interoperability across all levels between its extremities.

It is within the Informational layers of *Business Context* and *Semantic Understanding* in the middle of the Stack, that the IEC CIM can be deployed (Hargreaves et al., 2014). These layers constitute a bridge that transfers meaning in the form of syntactic conformity, semantic understanding, and context to the signals arising from the lower technical layers up to the Business Objectives and Policy layers. The IEC CIM aims at enabling interoperability in support of a functional SG.

Figure 5: A Typical SG organizational architecture identifying the role of the IEC CIM in supporting end-to-end interoperability (Hargreaves et al., 2014).

The IEC CIM is a scalable and extensible semantic model for power systems and a description of its design and class composition is given in the associated IEC Standards (IEC 61970, IEC 61968, and IEC 62325). It is object-oriented and presented as a UML class model. It defines a common vocabulary and basic ontology for aspects of the electric power industry.

The structure of the CIM is designed to be extensible and scalable; when new objects not available within the standard set are needed, they can be added easily, given the open nature of the standard model. Figure 6 represents the package overview of the CIM including packages from the standards IEC 61970-301, -302 and -303. Figure 7 represents an extract of CIM, the transformer model, expressed in a UML diagram.

3.2 Open Ontologies and Vocabularies

This subsection provides an overview of some of the existing, well-known, and open ontologies and vocabularies with a focus on various aspects of energy or power systems.

3.2.1 SAREF4ENER

In 2017, the ETSI, in collaboration with OneM2M⁷, published the standard ETSI TS 103 410-1 V1.1.1 (2017-01) (ETSI, 2017), which is based on the Smart Appliances REFerence (SAREF) ontology interoperability language. SAREF ontology was intended to enable interoperability

⁷<https://www.onem2m.org/>

Figure 6: Package overview of the CIM including packages from the standards IEC 61970-301, -302 and -303 (Uslar et al., n.d.).

between solutions from different providers and among various activity sectors in the IoT, thus contributing to the development of the global digital market. Figure 8 shows an overview of the main classes of SAREF and their relationships. SAREF focuses on the concept of a device, which is defined as *a tangible object designed to accomplish a particular task in households, common public buildings or offices*.

ETSI TS 103 410-1 V1.1.1 has standardized the first three extensions of SAREF dedicated to different domains. SAREF4ENER (ETSI, 2020a) is a Web Ontology Language Description Logic (OWL-DL) ontology that extends SAREF with new classes and properties, focused on demand response scenarios, in which customers can offer flexibility to the SG to manage their smart home devices by means of a Customer Energy Manager (CEM). SAREF4ENER has been created in collaboration with Energy@Home and EEBus.

Figure 9 provides an overview of the SAREF4ENER ontology. Rectangles containing an orange circle represent classes created in SAREF4ENER (“s4ener:” prefix before their identifier), while rectangles containing a faded orange circle represent classes reused from other ontologies, such as the SAREF ontology; rectangles that contain a list of values between square brackets denote an enumeration of individuals (ETSI, 2020a).

Figure 7: CIM extract expressed in a UML diagram: transformer model (Jang et al., 2013).

Figure 8: Overview of the SAREF ontology (ETSI, 2020b).

The hierarchy of classes and properties defined in the SAREF4ENER ontology are shown in Figure 10. Orange circles represent classes defined in the SAREF4ENER, while faded orange circles represent classes that are reused from other ontologies. Object properties - which are properties between two classes - are denoted by blue rectangles, while datatype properties - which are properties between a class and a data type, such as `xsd:string` or `xsd:dateTime`, are denoted by green rectangles. Faded blue and green rectangles denote object properties and datatype properties that are reused from other ontologies.

As an example, Figure 11 shows how the Device class is defined in the SAREF ontology and Figure 12 shows how the Device class has been extended in the SAREF4ENER ontology.

Figure 10: SAREF4ENER class and property hierarchy (ETSI, 2020a).

Figure 11: Device class in the SAREF ontology (ETSI, 2020b).

Figure 12: Device class extended in the SAREF4ENER ontology (ETSI, 2020a).

entities, such as qualities and other attributes.

As shown in Figure 13, the OEO consists of three main domain-specific modules covering the following aspects of the energy systems analysis domain:

- models and data (o eo-model);
- social and economic aspects (o eo-social);
- the physical side of energy systems (o eo-physical).

Moreover, the OEO includes an additional module for classes and relations that are needed in multiple modules (o eo-shared).

Among the imported modules, a subset of the Relations Ontology (RO) module contains a subset of the object properties defined by the RO (Smith et al., 2005), the ones that are relevant for energy systems analysis. Examples of object properties that have been imported are properties such as “has quality” and “has disposition”, some basic properties such as “part of”,

Figure 13: Modules of the OEO (Booshehri et al., 2021).

and properties to define temporal and spatial relations including “starts with” and “located in”. Moreover, all metadata annotations (e.g., “document” or “reference”), along with some important classes that are useful for all modules, defined by the Information Artifact Ontology (IAO)⁹ have been included in the oeo-model module.

An overview of a subset of classes and properties of the OEO is illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Overview of a subset of classes and properties of the OEO (Open energy Platform ontology GitHub repository, n.d.).

3.2.3 Ontology for Energy Management Applications

Ontology for Energy Management Applications (OEMA) (Cuenca et al., 2017) is an attempt to unify existing heterogeneous ontologies that represent different energy-related data.

⁹<https://obofoundry.org/ontology/iao.html>

Several research projects and initiatives have proposed semantic ontologies to represent data related to the energy domain used by different SG Energy Management Systems (EMSs) deployed in different SG scenarios: Smart Homes, urban environments (e.g., building, district, city, etc.), organizations, microgrids or Virtual Power Plants (VPPs) and SG Demand Response (DR) management. Figure 15 shows the level of detail with which some of the available reviewed energy ontologies represent the main energy domains. An ontology represents an energy domain with a high level of detail when it includes a wide variety of terms and complex class hierarchies about that domain, a medium level of detail when it includes fewer terms and less complex class hierarchies, and lastly, a low-level of detail when it includes only few classes and virtually no class hierarchies. As reported in Figure 16, none of the reviewed ontologies represents all types of energy performance and contextual data that should be taken into account for energy management, and the data are represented at different levels of detail. Furthermore, different terms are used to represent the same energy concepts.

ontology \ energy domain	ThinkHome ontology [11]	SAREF4EE ontology [18]	BOnSAI ontology [7]	ProSGV3 ontology [9]
Infrastructure technical data	H	L	M	M
Energy consumption systems data	H	M	L	H
Energy performance data	H	H	H	H
Sensors/actuators data	H	M	M	M
Energy stakeholders' data	M	-	L	L
Weather/climate data	H	L	L	M
Geographical data	-	-	-	L
Environmental data	M	-	M	-
Distributed energy sources data	M	L	L	M
Energy DR operations	-	M	-	L

Figure 15: Energy domains representation level of detail (H=High/M=Medium/L=Low) (Cuenca et al., 2017).

The OEMA ontology network (Cuenca, 2018b) is made up of eight interconnected domain ontologies. Each ontology represents one or various energy domains. These ontologies are connected by a core ontology. The OEMA top-level structure is shown in Figure 17.

The OEMA Infrastructure Ontology¹⁰ contains data about infrastructures/buildings, including infrastructure/building types (e.g., household, microgrid, etc.), technical data (e.g., material, surface, etc.), spaces data (e.g., floors, rooms, etc.), geometrical data (e.g., floor area), etc.

The OEMA Energy and Equipment Ontology¹¹ represents energy equipment, such as building automation system resources (e.g., sensors, actuators/controllers and HVAC systems), industrial equipment (e.g., construction and manufacturing equipment), energy generators (e.g., Electric Vehicles, Home Power Plants, etc.), loads (white and brown goods), power storage/energy carriers, etc. The ontology also represents the energy equipment features, such as devices power curve and power profile or device state.

¹⁰<http://www.purl.org/oema/infrastructure>

¹¹<http://www.purl.org/oema/enaeq>

Energy domain	Ontology	Reused concepts
Energy consumption systems data	ThinkHome ontology	HVAC systems, communication appliances, entertainment appliances, office automation devices, lighting systems, white goods, acoustic systems, domotic network components, energy facilities, device state, device commands, equipment manufacturer, external and internal equipment
	SAREF4EE ontology	Appliances working modes and power profiles, device manufacturer and device model.
	EnergyUse ontology	Wearable devices.
	ProSGV3 ontology	Body care devices, pressing devices, water heating devices, charging devices, lighting systems, entertainment devices, cleaning devices and electrical appliance category.

Figure 16: Ontologies and concepts reused in the OEMA (Cuenca et al., 2017).

The OEMA Geographical Ontology¹² represents geographical data about infrastructures and energy equipment locations. These data include populated places (e.g., country, city, district, etc.), natural places (e.g., mountain, sea, etc.), and places geographical attributes such as altitude, depth, or area.

Figure 17: OEMA ontology network structure (Cuenca et al., 2017)

¹²<http://www.purl.org/oema/geographical>

The OEMA External Factors Ontology¹³ captures external factors that can influence energy usage. These factors include climate type (e.g., alpine, continental, etc.), environmental conditions (e.g., lighting, noise, etc.), household socio-economic factors (e.g., household income, housing price, etc.), people's socio-economic factors (e.g., salary, education level, etc.), population socioeconomic factors (e.g., density, main origin, etc.), and weather phenomenon (e.g., temperature), etc.

The OEMA Person and Organisation Ontology¹⁴ represents person and organisation data: person and person attributes (e.g., age, gender, etc.), organisation, organisation internal structure (e.g., departments), organisations economic data (e.g., endowment, net income, etc.), person roles in organisations (e.g., role in project, occupation), etc.

The OEMA Energy Saving Ontology represents general and personalized energy-saving recommendations.

Figure 18: Main energy domains represented by the OEMA ontology network (Cuenca, 2018b).

The OEMA Smart Grid Stakeholder Ontology¹⁵ represents SG stakeholders and roles in the energy market (e.g., energy consumers, energy suppliers, Distribution System Operators (DSOs), etc.) and energy flexibility operations, (e.g., market processes, flex-offers exchange), etc.

The OEMA Units Ontology¹⁶ represents different units of measure used by the OEMA domain ontologies (e.g., energy units, area units, capacity units, currency, density units, etc.). The OEMA Units of Measurement ontology is reused by OEMA infrastructure, Energy and Equipment, geographical, and External Factors ontologies.

¹³<http://www.purl.org/oema/externalfactors>

¹⁴<http://www.purl.org/oema/pao>

¹⁵<http://www.purl.org/oema/sgstakeholders>

¹⁶<http://www.purl.org/oema/units>

The diagram represented in fig. 18 shows the relations between the main energy domains represented by the OEMA ontology network.

3.2.4 SmArt eneRGy dOmain oNtology (SARGON)

The IoT is a paradigm where the fragmentation of standards, platforms, services, and technologies, is often scattered among different vertical domains, and, consequently, the smart energy system is one of the vertical domains in which IoT technology is investigated. In the early stages of studying the IoT domains that deal with big data and interoperability, a semantic layer can be served to approach the difficulty of heterogeneity in information and data representation from IoT devices. In 2015, the SAREF ontology (see 3.2.1), was developed to interconnect data of smart devices and facilitate the communication between IoT devices that use different protocols and standards. The SmArt eneRGy dOmain oNtology (SARGON) is an extension of the SAREF ontology to cross-cut domain-specific information that represents the smart energy domain and is powered by smart energy standards and IoT initiatives, as well as real use cases. SARGON involves classes, properties, and instances explicitly created to cover the building and electrical grid automation domain.

As a basis for the SARGON, a set of use cases and existing data models have been identified and they can be summarised as follows (Haghighi et al., 2020):

1. Automation of medium voltage distribution grids: it considers the inclusion of DC technology for which the grid is operated as a hybrid AC–DC power grid. For this use case, the Intelligent Electronic Device (IED) is used to monitor the grid. Currently, the standard IEC-61850 constitutes a well-received reference for the automation of distribution grids. The extension proposed in SARGON consists of reformulating the data structure used in IEC-61850 according to an ontology description, as well as introducing devices specifically related to hybrid AC/DC grids, such as power converters or DC switches;
2. PMU interaction and data visualisation: Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) find more and more applications in the monitoring and control of the electrical grid, not only in the transmission networks but also in the distribution ones. The PMUs interaction with the connected devices, as well as the data-driven applications that exploit the obtained measurements, constitute a worthwhile field for the SAREF expansion. Therefore, PMU as a type of metering device is included in the SARGON ontology;
3. Building automation and monitoring: The control of energy demand in buildings such as gas, electricity, hot water, etc. and its optimisation. It involves the deployment of Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS), which relies on the interaction with smart meters and actuator devices for the effective operation of each functionality. Moreover, user involvement in the overall process is an undeniable constituent, which has to be included in the ontology representation of the building automation domain;
4. Energy management with residential/non-residential involvement: In order to optimise the overall energy management with residential/non-residential involvement, the utilities have to expand the energy control. Therefore, the SARGON must include the entire city district, as building agglomeration. Control algorithms are implemented on local hardware Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) and the connection between the PLC, sensors, and actuators is frequently realised by either wired analog signals (0–10 V) or by wired bus systems. SARGON has been considered for the modern building energy systems, especially in residential/non-residential buildings, which includes plenty of sensors and actuators in order to achieve a proper operation besides the building operation task;

Figure 19: OEMA Energy and Equipment Ontology main classes and top-level relations (Cuenca, 2018a).

5. Energy management at the building/district level: It targets the interaction between the energy management of buildings/districts and their electrical automation. Hence, it considers the control functionalities and the data/measurements that involve the combination of both these aspects. For instance, SARGON includes use cases to control the installed electrical devices in the building. For this reason, it has a building information domain connected to the list of devices defined for building automation and electrical system monitoring.

Figure 20 gives a picture of the complexity of the SARGON ontology, which aggregates cross-cut domain-specific information. Modularity is one of the main advantages of the SARGON ontology; this allows further development of new elements necessary to fill possible gaps and supports any additional development of missing information models.

Figure 20: Overview of the SARGON ontology (Haghgoo et al., 2020).

The SARGON ontology network consists of several interconnected domain ontologies related to the SG and building automation:

- Person, Company, Building, and Address ontologies contain data for describing the nature of a person, company, building, and address, besides spaces and geometrical data such as area, place, floors, etc.;
- Device inherits all classes of SAREF ontology and extends it according to energy equipment which includes industrial equipment, energy generators, and system resources, such as PMUs, Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers, converters, etc.;
- Services provides ontologies for services in the SG and building automation like controlling, monitoring and protection;
- CIM and IEC 61850 present terms and relations in the power grids. It identifies the list of classes and variant instances that can be used for monitoring and controlling of SGs according to the standards.

The ontologies of the SARGON network have been harmonized to enable data portability for different applications in smart energy systems including, but not limited, to building automation and power grid controlling/monitoring. They are intended to be used together with FIWARE NGSI-LD, a standard defined by ETSI Industry Specification Group for cross-cutting Context Information Management (GS, 2020). The ontology covers Building and Device domains and

connects these two domains according to the concept of Linked-Data. Figure 21 represents the graph visualization of the ontology with a view of classes in Web Protégé ¹⁷.

Figure 21: SARGON view in Web Protégé

3.2.5 Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology

The Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology (DABGEO) (Ariza et al., 2020) is a reusable and usable global ontology for the energy domain that provides a common representation of energy domains represented by existing energy ontologies. The DABGEO includes 97 modules available at the DABGEO home page (*DABGEO: Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology*, 2019). The ontology is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.01.

The DABGEO has been developed to be reused by different energy management applications, which can be classified into five main application types according to the SG scenario or infrastructure where they are deployed: Smart Home energy management applications, building/district/city energy management applications, organization energy management applications, microgrid energy management applications and SG DR management applications. The DABGEO provides interoperability between energy management applications that operate in different scenarios. Figure 22 depicts the DABGEO high-level structure.

The DABGEO represents the following energy domains:

- Energy Equipment domain (Figure 23): data about energy equipment such as consumption systems (e.g., home appliances, Heating Ventilation and Air-Conditioning (HVAC) systems), renewable and non-renewable energy sources (e.g., photovoltaics, fuel oils)

¹⁷<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/acs/public/ontology/sargon/-/tree/master>

Figure 22: DABGEO ontology high-level structure (Ariza et al., 2020)

and power storage devices (e.g., batteries). This domain also includes data about energy equipment features and operational aspects such as device power profile or device state;

- Infrastructure domain (Figure 24): different types of infrastructures and buildings (e.g., homes, industrial infrastructures, campuses, microgrids, power plants, etc.), building/infrastructure features (e.g., surface, material, etc.), geometrical details (rooms, floors, etc.) and internal and external environmental conditions (e.g., room temperature, etc.);
- Energy Performance Data domain (Figure 25): energy performance values (energy production, consumption, and storage values) of devices and infrastructures and energy Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as infrastructure energy cost or energy gain;
- Energy External factors domain (Figure 26): data about external factors that may affect energy usage. These factors include infrastructure location data (e.g., latitude and longitude, state, city), weather/climate data (weather conditions and weather forecast), environmental data (e.g., air pollutants and their indicators), and demography and socio-economic data (e.g., population density, population main origin, person education level);
- SG Stakeholders domain (Figure 27): data about SG stakeholders, such as individual users (e.g., home users, building occupants, employees) and organizations (e.g., corporations, educational institutions). It also encompasses the roles that SG stakeholders have in the energy market such as energy consumers, energy suppliers or DSOs.

The DABGEO ontology follows a layered structure to provide a balance of reusability-usability:

- The common-domain layer represents the top-level concept of each domain in one ontology module;
- The variant-domain layer includes the variant domain knowledge reused only in several SG scenarios;
- The domain-task layer includes the domain knowledge reused in specific SG scenarios. The Scenario sub-layer represents the knowledge relevant to a certain SG scenario. The

Figure 23: Representation of the Energy Equipment domain in DABGEO (DABGEO: Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology, 2019).

application type sub-layer represents the knowledge reused only by certain energy management application types for a specific SG scenario.

3.2.6 Energy Grid Ontology for Digital Twins

The Azure IoT engineering team has been collaborating with customers, domain experts, and industry-standard organizations to develop Digital Twins Definition Language (DTD) ontologies by exploiting existing industry ontologies and best practices. After having published the DTD ontologies for smart buildings based on RealEstateCore, and for smart cities based on ETSI NGSI-LD (GS, 2020), the Azure team has released the Energy Grid Ontology (*opendigitaltwins-energygrid GitHub repository, 2021*), an adaptation from CIM (see section 3.1.2). The CIM-based DTD ontology contextualise data and defines properties of various grid entities and the relationships among them.

The CIM organizes entities into distinct packages. The first release of the Energy Grid Ontology includes core, wire, and generation packages, and prosumer-related entities from the metering, customer, and DER packages (Figure 28). The Core Package contains the PowerSystemResource, ConductingEquipment, and common collections of those entities shared by all applications. The Wire Package is an extension to the Core that provides model information on the electrical characteristics of transmission and distribution networks. The Generation Package has information for unit commitment and economic dispatch of hydro and thermal

Figure 24: Representation of the Infrastructure domain in DABGEO (DABGEO: Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology, 2019).

Figure 25: Representation of the Energy Performance domain in DABGEO (DABGEO: Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology, 2019).

generating units, load forecasting, automatic generation control, and unit modelling for training

Figure 26: Representation of the Energy External factors domain in DABGEO (DABGEO: Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology, 2019).

Figure 27: Representation of the Energy Staholders domain in DABGEO (DABGEO: Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology, 2019).

simulation. Lastly, the Prosumer Package includes various entities related to consumer and DER (e.g., EquivalentLoad, UsagePoints, and MeterReading).

Figure 28: CIM packages included in the first release of the Energy Grid Ontology (opendigitaltwins-energygrid GitHub repository, 2021).

3.2.7 SEAS Knowledge Model and Electrical Power System Ontology

The Smart Energy Aware Systems (SEAS) knowledge model is a modularized and versioned ontology with four basic modules that explain, among other things, physical systems and their connections, value association for their attributes, and the actions involved in such value association. The first core module is the `seas:FeatureOfInterestOntology`. It offers a design pattern for describing qualifiable, measurable, observable, or actionable features of interest (e.g., a room) and their attributes (e.g., its temperature). The second core module is the `seas:EvaluationOntology`. It contains design patterns for describing and qualifying property evaluations (qualification or quantification). It offers design patterns for describing and qualifying property evaluations including the kind of evaluation and its Spatio-temporal validity context. The third core module is `seas:SystemOntology`. It specifies a design pattern for connecting systems through connection points. This design pattern may be used to represent zones (systems) within a building that share a boundary, for example (connections). The characteristics of a system are frequently state variables (e.g., agent population, temperature), whereas the characteristics of a link generally flow (e.g., heat flow). The fourth and final core module is the Process Execution Platform (PEP) ontology, which is an externalized module that generalizes the W3C Semantic Sensor Network (SSN)¹⁸ ontology and describes `pep:ProcessExecutors` (sensors, actuators, web services, and so on) that use `pep:Executes` and processes `pep:ProcessExecutions`. On top of these core modules, the SEAS ontology defines multiple vertical modules, each of which instantiates one or more core ontology patterns and is often domain-specific (Lefrançois, 2017; Lefrançois et al., 2016).

Below are some examples of such vertical modules.

- `seas:ElectricPowerSystemOntology` defines system types (e.g., `seas:ElectricPowerLine`, `seas:ElectricPowerProducer`), their connections through which they exchange energy (e.g., `seas:SplitPhasePowerBus`), their properties (e.g.,

¹⁸<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>

- electric power system connection points, via which electricity flows in and out of the power networks.

These concepts are represented by the following five main classes in ontology:

1. seas:ElectricPowerSystem;
2. seas:exchangesElectricityWith;
3. seas:subElectricPowerSystemOf;
4. seas:ElectricalConnection;
5. seas:ElectricalConnectionPoint.

There are functional properties, classification of voltage and its variations in addition to having sub-classes, to the main five classes, to represent the concepts in a more fine-grained fashion. As an example, the following are the sub-classes for the seas:ElectricPowerSystem:

1. seas:ElectricPowerConsumer;
2. seas:ElectricPowerProducer;
3. seas:ElectricPowerStorageSystem;
4. seas:ElectricPowerTransmissionSystem.

3.2.8 OntoPowSys ontology

The OntoPowSys ontology (Devanand et al., 2020) is a domain ontology capable of formally representing energy management strategies in a multi-domain, heterogeneous industrial network like an Eco-Industrial Park (EIP). It focuses on the power systems domain and provides a framework for integrating this knowledge with the other domains of an EIP. The OntoPowSys ontology is expressed using a Description Logic (DL) syntax and the OWL2 language has been used to represent it.

The OntoPowSys ontology extends the upper layer modules of the OntoEIP ontology, which encompass all the broader concepts relevant to an EIP (Figure 30). In turn, OntoEIP has been borrowed from the OntoCAPE ontology, which represents representing knowledge in the chemical engineering domain, with additional lower-level modules for extending the wider concepts in an EIP.

Figure 30: Abstraction layering in the OntoPowSys ontology with the uppermost layer showing most generic concepts (Devanand et al., 2020).

Figure 31 presents the definition of all the terms of the OntoPowSys ontology. In the OntoPowSys knowledge base, the PowerSystem concept is subsumed by CompositeSystem concept in the OntoEIP. A typical power system consists of a set of power generators that are connected to their respective power loads through a power grid consisting of buses. It also has devices like power converters to manage the quality and quantity of power flow. The subsystems are aligned with the conventional structure of generation, transmission, and consumption. The generation is expressed as PowerGenerator concept name, which is subsumed by two other concepts *DispatchableUnits* and *Non-DispatchableUnits*, based on the nature of their generation. These generators are considered as power sources with a set of rated electrical parameters. Similarly, power loads are considered as generic power sinks with a set of rated parameters.

OntoPowSys is used to represent all the possible types of electrical consumption from individual devices level (e.g., pumps, motors etc.) to clusters of loads (e.g., districts, buildings etc.). Critical loads and controllable loads, which offer some flexibility in power dispatch problems in the framework of demand response, are represented in the ontology.

Bus nodes constitute the transmission network of a power system and form the power grid topology. Power injection and consumption at a bus help to compute the power flow. A bus node act as a physical point of connection between two electrical devices. The concept name *ElectricalLine* connects the buses using *hasInput* and *hasOutput* role names that are subsumed by *isConnectedTo* role name.

Term name	Definition
Power generator	A generator is a rotating device that converts kinetic energy into electrical energy for use in an external circuit.
Power load	A power load is an electrical component or portion of a circuit that consumes electric power.
Energy storage system	Energy storage is the capture of energy produced at one time for use at a later time.
Transmission network	It is an interconnected network for delivering electricity from generating stations to loads.
Power converter	Power converter is an electronic switching device for converting electrical energy from one form to another such as AC-DC, DC-AC or change in frequency.
Power transformer	The Power transformer is a static device,that transfers electrical energy from one circuit to another. It is commonly used to step up or step down voltage levels.
Rectifier	A static electrical device which converts an alternating current into a direct current by allowing a current to flow through it in one direction only.
Inverter	A static electrical device which converts direct current into alternating current.
Dispatchable units	Dispatchable units of generation refers to sources of electricity that can be used on demand and dispatched at the request of power grid operators, according to market needs.
Non dispatchable units	A non-dispatchable source of electricity generate electrical energy but cannot be turned on or off in order to meet societies fluctuating electricity needs.
Energy source	A source from which useful energy can be extracted or recovered either directly or by means of a conversion or transformation process.
Current type	Electric current comes in two varieties: alternating current and direct current, abbreviated as AC and DC.
Voltage Regulator	A voltage regulator is a system designed to automatically maintain a constant voltage level.
Bus node	A bus network is an arrangement in a local area network (LAN) in which each node (workstation or other device) is connected to a main cable or link called the bus.
Electrical Line	An electrical line is a cable (above ground or underground), along which electricity is passed to an area or building.
Switch	A switch is an electrical component that can "make" or "break" an electrical circuit, interrupting the current or diverting it from one conductor to another.
Energy meter	An energy meter is a device that measures the amount of electric energy consumed by a residence, a business, or an electrically powered device.
Rated power	The rated power of an equipment is the highest power input allowed to flow through particular equipment.
Rated efficiency	Rated energy efficiency is a ratio of the amount of energy that is usefully used compared with the total energy input to obtain that useful output.
Rated current	Rated current is that current for which the equipment or the machine has been designed.
Rated voltage	Rated voltage is that voltage for which the equipment or the machine has been designed.
Active power	The power which is actually consumed or utilized in an AC Circuit is called True power or Active Power. It is measured in terms of watt.
Reactive power	Reactive power is the part of complex power (Apparent Power) that corresponds to storage and retrieval of energy rather than consumption of power.It results from dissipation from inductive and capacitive loads, measured in terms of VAR (volt-ampere reactive).

Figure 31: OntoPowSys term definitions (Devanand et al., 2020).

Energy storage, which is represented in the knowledge base by *EnergyStorageSystem*, is a subsystem of the power system and allows more flexibility in order to modify a load curve (e.g., peak shaving, load shifting) or support the integration of renewables. Based on the concept definition of the state of charge these types of equipment can behave either as power sources or power sinks within their operating limits.

Finally, power converters (PowerConverter concept in the knowledge base) realise the energy flow from one form of electrical energy to another. Transformers allow conversion from one AC voltage level to another while typical converters realise DC and AC conversion. The number of properties attached to those converters is higher than the other grid components as the ratings refer both the input and output sides. One important property of the converters is whether they allow the bidirectional flow of energy, like batteries, or uni-directional flow, like low voltage supply transformers.

3.2.9 OntoMG ontology

The advent of “smart” technologies and equipment and the growing integration of renewable energy sources in the power grid has led to the emergence of new services and opportunities in the electricity domain. Power systems are evolving towards “connected systems” composed of several components where each has a different role and (direct/indirect) impact on the entire environment and microgrids are a good example of this. Microgrids aim to provide reliable power by incorporating local generation units/systems based on renewable and conventional power sources, energy storage systems, and energy consumption loads and are able to operate in grid-connected mode or islanded mode. Microgrids enhance efficient power distribution and cost-effectiveness, by the installation of power sources nearby the consumers’ loads. Due to the intermittent nature of the renewable energy sources and the exposure of the microgrid to predictable and non-predictable events (e.g., anomalies, storms, etc.), an ontology modelling of the microgrid could be crucial to let the microgrid components act and react autonomously or collectively according to a certain event since it can represent beliefs, goals, hypotheses, and predictions. For instance, a diesel generator should stop working automatically when renewable energy sources are able to satisfy all the loads’ power demands. In (Salameh et al., 2015), Salameh et al. present OntoMG, an ontology-based information model that aims to resolve interoperability issues encountered in a microgrid and to achieve its functionalities and objectives. This work was done in collaboration with Jema Irizar Group, leader of the ISare project.

The OntoMG ontology is based on the IEC CIM and on the IEC 61850 standards and integrates six packages each related to a specific aspect involved in the achievement of the microgrid objectives:

1. identification aspect (Id), related to the component’s unique identity in the system;
2. operation aspect (Op), related to the component’s operating;
3. mobility (Mob) aspect related to the component displacements during their lifetime;
4. economical aspect (Eco), related to the components’ participation in the Energy Market;
5. ecological aspect (Ecolo), related to the component’s participation and effects in/on the environment, 6) multi-roles aspect, related to the component roles during his operating in the system.

3.2.10 Ontology for Power Transformer Fault Diagnosis

In (SAMIRMI et al., 2015), Samirmi et al. presents a novel fuzzy ontology reasoner for power transformer fault diagnosis under a multiagent framework. The developed ontology provides a comprehensive knowledge base as part of a multi-agent system to enable imprecision reasoning. The power transformer is one of the most important pieces of equipment in electric power

Figure 32: Extract of the ISare-OntoMG information model (Salameh et al., 2015).

systems, which converts voltage to higher or lower levels. All industries require a safe and reliable supply of power all the time and any failure in power transformers may cause losses to the industry supplied by these transformers. Therefore, the operation reliability of a transformer is very important and can be improved with online transformer condition monitoring and fault diagnosis using a dedicated knowledge-based system.

Figure 33: Main classes and properties of the developed basic ontology for the transformer fault diagnosis (SAMIRMI et al., 2015).

Figure 34: The developed basic ontology for power transformer fault diagnosis (SAMIRMI et al., 2015).

To build an appropriate ontology for power transformer fault diagnosis, three main categories are defined as subclasses of class Transformer: fault, symptom, and component (Figure 33). The fault category contains various fault types, defined by some types of properties according to the symptom category.

Figure 34 shows the developed basic ontology for power transformer fault diagnosis. In the research activity, the communication between the developed basic ontology and the power transformer is handled by an agent.

3.2.11 A domain ontology on cascading effects in critical infrastructures

Microgrids are a growing segment of the energy industry that represents the paradigm shift from remote central station power plants toward more localized, distributed generation. The ability to isolate from the main grid makes microgrids resilient, and the ability to conduct flexible, parallel operations permits the delivery of services that make the grid more competitive. By “islanding” from the grid in case of emergencies, a microgrid can both continue serving its included load when the grid is down and serve its surrounding community by providing a platform to support critical services. Microgrids power Critical Infrastructures (CIs) and are themselves CIs.

on cascading failure effects in critical infrastructures, that enables a better understanding of how cascading effects are generated and propagated, how they can be analysed, and how to mitigate their impact on CIs.

Figure 37: Analysis approach model (Santoro et al., 2022).

The research literature concerning the cascading effects in CIs provided the essential information (concepts, relationships and definitions) to build the ontology model depicted in Figure 35. It was possible to identify some limitations in the proposed model, namely the lack of a deeper analysis of the concepts of risk and their management. The final model of the cascading effects ontology is present in Figure 36, Figure 37, Figure 38, and Figure 39.

Figure 38: Resilience model (Santoro et al., 2022).

3.2.12 Ontology for fault detection

In (Li et al., 2022), Tingting Li et al. presents a semantic model-based approach for building fault detection approach for building energy systems. The idea is to reproduce the reasoning of the human experts in understanding massive amounts of operational data of various buildings, and further proposing customized fault detection solutions. Semantic rules written in abstract syntax are proposed to detect the operation problems, control problems, equipment malfunction and sensor failure in building energy systems. Those rules can be reused in various building

Figure 39: Threat agent model (Santoro et al., 2022).

Figure 40: Threat agent model (Santoro et al., 2022).

energy systems. For a target system, the building data are mapped to the ontology to generate a customized knowledge graph that captures the physics underlying the system operations (Figure 41, Figure 42, and Figure 43). The semantic rules are activated based on the knowledge graph to detect the faults. The knowledge graph is automatically updated with new data step by step. The fault action mechanisms are captured based on the inference chains of the rules. Experts can find the fault reasons and take action for commissioning. The results obtained show that the approach is powerful in providing customized fault detection solutions for different situations. It has high levels of interpretability, reliability, and automation

3.2.13 Ontology for cybersecurity

In (Hutschenreuter et al., 2021), Hutschenreuter, Helmar et al. present a semantic model-based approach for building fault detection approach for building energy systems. They propose a novel resilience framework by combining a Security Information and Event Management Systems (SIEM) for detecting cyber-attacks with ontologies and an inference system for supporting the selection of measures during cyber incidents and Information Technology (IT) infrastructure failures in an automatic way.

Figure 41: Overview of the ontology for fault detection (Li et al., 2022).

Figure 42: Relations among the main concepts of the ontology for fault detection (Li et al., 2022).

The ontology of IT infrastructures provides explicit knowledge about real IT systems and enables reasoning based on this knowledge. The IT infrastructure is divided into two groups: Hard-IT and Soft-IT infrastructures. The Soft-IT infrastructure is used by people to access stored data or use services available in Hard-IT infrastructures. Security measures will be applied to both IT infrastructures.

Figure 44 shows the static part (TBox in the following) of the ontology for the Hard-IT. If a physical network connection has to be assigned to several networks, for example by using Virtual Local Area Networks, it has to be modelled by several parallel network connections. Other classes and roles of the Hard-IT infrastructure are to be interpreted in a similar manner.

For its practical usage, in addition to the TBox, the dynamic part (ABox) of the ontology needs to be modelled as well. An ABox contains concrete instances of the classes and roles. For example, there may be two instances of the class PC (PC1 and PC2) and one instance of the class WiredLink (WLink1). Subsequently, the connectedToLink role should be used to describe the connection between PC1/PC2 and WLink1, so that it can be possible to infer that PC1 and PC2 are connected to each other. the TBox and an ABox together represent the following knowledge about an infrastructure:

Figure 43: Extract of the ontology for fault detection (Li et al., 2022).

Figure 44: TBox for Hard-IT Infrastructures (Hutschenreuter et al., 2021).

1. The location of the Hard-IT components within the buildings and rooms;
2. The physical connection between different components of the Hard-IT (The IT devices are wired in a way that an appropriate configuration of them enables an actual network connection);
3. The places where security measures can be applied on the Hard-IT level.

Figure 45 displays the modelling of the TBox for the Soft-IT which is divided into Object and Subject classes. These classes are inspired by an Access Control model where subjects (entities, e.g., users, programs, processes) have certain permissions to access objects (e.g., data, programs, devices) based on AC policies. Elements of the Soft-IT infrastructure cannot exist outside the Hard-IT infrastructure and, therefore, all instances of the classes Subject and Object must be assigned to actual devices of the Hard-IT. The TBox and an ABox represent the following knowledge about the Soft-IT infrastructure:

Figure 45: TBox for Soft-IT Infrastructures (Hutschenreuter et al., 2021).

Figure 46: TBox for Cybersecurity (Hutschenreuter et al., 2021).

1. The possible accesses of subjects to objects;
2. The places where security measures can be applied on the Soft-IT level.

Figure 46 represents the TBox for cybersecurity. The bottom left depicts the TBox for the orga-

nizational structure via the class `BusinessProcess` to represent business processes, the class `Role` to represent organizational positions, and the class `Employee` to model employees who fill certain positions of a company. Infrastructures are required for the execution of business processes and this is expressed by the role `needsInfrastructure` and its inverse role `runsBusinessProcess`. Infrastructures are indirectly accessed via roles that are assigned to responsible employees of an organization. The connection of responsible employees to infrastructures is given by the roles `hasRole` and `accessesInfrastructure` with corresponding reverse roles `filledByEmployee` and `isControlledByRole`. The following knowledge is represented by this part of the TBox and an ABox about a single organizational structure:

1. The responsible people who should be informed in the case of a cyber threat;
2. The responsible people who should carry out technical or organizational measures.

The need for protection is represented in the ontology by relating the infrastructure to the security objectives.

4 Proposed Methodology

One of the main goals of the HYPERRIDE project is to achieve a higher level of interoperability. Interoperability, as defined in Section 2.1, is a challenging quality attribute to achieve because it necessitates a thorough understanding of the problem, the solution, and their interrelation. Data is at the center of interoperability, necessitating its consideration in any effort for achieving a higher level of interoperability. This task is dealing with developing an interoperable data model for hybrid AC/DC electrical power systems. However, any such attempt would be too challenging without having a well-defined methodology that should help in understanding the problem, the solution, and their interrelationship. One such methodology has been developed for this task and is presented in this section.

4.1 Overview

Among the main guiding principles for a suitable methodology is its ability to provide an understanding of the problem, the solution, and its interrelationship. It should also have the ability to look for existing patterns and solutions to similar problems and solutions. An overview of the methodology is presented in Figure 47 below. As can be seen in the diagram, the methodology consists of four phases. These four phases help in being consistent with the design guiding principle. The *understand* phase help is understanding the problem, the *explore* phase helps is looking for patterns and solutions to similar problems in the literature and field, based on the inputs from the two previous phases, the *develop* phase is then able to make an interoperable data model and finally, the *validate* phase is used to see to what degree the proposed solution is able to solve the problem. Furthermore, the fact that the application of this methodology is an iterative process is highlighted in the diagram.

Below, a more detailed description of the individual phases is provided.

Figure 47: An overview of the proposed methodology.

4.2 The Understand Phase

This phase is dedicated to understanding the problem. Here various requirements and constraints are to be collected in addition to defining the scope of the data model and details about

the domain representation in the ontology are collected and refined. During this phase, the output from various other work packages is considered as the input. More specifically, the main inputs are requirements and use cases from WP2, the ICT architecture from WP5, and pilot configuration and implementation plans from WP6, WP7, and WP8 for the Swiss, Italian and German pilots, respectively. Figure 48 shows an overview of the interactions of this task with other work packages.

Figure 48: An overview of the inputs for the Understand phase.

4.3 The Explore Phase

The pattern and solutions for problems similar to or closely related to the Hybrid AC/DC power system are planned to be investigated in this phase using a state-of-the-art analysis based on literature, industry and field applications, international standards, data models, and ontologies, among other sources. These inputs are highlighted in Figure 49 below. Some of the outcomes from these phases have been documented in Section 2 and its subsections.

4.4 The Develop Phase

After sufficient inputs have been gathered from the *Understand* and *Explore* phases, this phase is then dedicated to the development of the interoperable data model.

Sufficient input would mean that some questions, listed below, can be reliably answered.

- What will be the domain and scope of the ontology?
- What will be the primary use of this ontology?
- What information needs to be available in this ontology?
- What type of question the ontology should be able to answer?
- What are some of the existing ontologies, data models, standards, etc. that can be used as the basis for our ontology?

Figure 49: An overview of the Explore phase.

In a nutshell, the development process would begin with the identification of the main concepts, classes, constraints, and relationships, followed by the formalization of this domain knowledge in an ontology.

4.5 The Validate Phase

The ontology must be validated for its *coherence* and *classification* after it has been created. The coherency test evaluates the ontology's completeness in representing the domain's required concepts, whereas the classification test evaluates the ontology's ability to infer various concepts that are not explicitly defined.

Figure 50: Ontology validation overview.

A software tool known as a description logic reasoner, a rule reasoning engine, a semantic reasoning engine, or simply a *reasoner* can be used to perform ontology validation. As inputs, the *reasoner* receives the ontology definition along with some instances of its concepts. Using this input, the reasoner can then decide 1) coherence: if the corresponding concepts are available in the ontology, and 2) inference: if the ontology definition is rich enough to deduce some concepts that are not explicitly defined. The requirements collected in the *Understand* phase (see Section 4.2), will be the primary source for preparing this input.

5 Hybrid AC/DC Ontology

This section introduces the developed HADGO. This includes providing an overview and design principles in Section 5.1, and the major entity classes are introduced in Section 5.2. More details about the axioms, data, and object properties are provided in Appendix A.

5.1 Scope and Overview

The HADGO is developed to help in defining, modeling, and analyzing a hybrid AC/DC power grid that can then be used in different use cases in the context of the H2020 HYPERRIDE project and beyond. Some of these use cases that were considered during the formulation of the ontology include but are not limited to power-flow calculation, cascading effects calculation, critical components identification, etc. However, the demonstration of such applications is beyond the scope of this document.

An overview of the HADGO is presented in Figure 51. The figure is very detailed and shows not only the entity classes and their relationships but also highlights the object properties that are used for such relationships as well as the entity class that is the domain and range of these properties. The ontology contains around 50 asserted entity classes. From these entity classes, Figure 52 highlights (half) the classes at the top two layers.

Additionally, the ontology contains around 186 axioms with 116 logical axioms with a number of object and data properties. Section 5.2 will provide an introduction to some of these entity classes; however, more details can be found in Appendix A. Adopting the naming convention usually used in ontology authoring, a prefix of `hadgo` is used with all the members of the HADGO ontology making the name following the format `hadgo:<member>`.

Developing data models in a diverse and uncoordinated manner typically results in textitdata stovepipes issues, which can lead to a total/partial failure in attaining interoperability and impede the ontology's reusability potential while also making integration difficult. When developed in a proper manner, ontologies can help in achieving consistency in the usage of terms and meaning leading towards achieving a common understanding and further avoiding frequent adoptions (Rudnicki, Smith, Malyuta, & Mandrick, 2016).

Ontological realism (Smith & Ceusters, 2010), is being advocated as one of the best practices (Alfaifi, 2022; Rudnicki et al., 2016) for ontology development. It refers to developing an ontology to be more like a reality model than a data model in order to maximize its utility and stability. In this development method, the resulting ontologies serve as representations of the entities to which the data pertains rather than the data itself.

In an interconnected knowledge/data ecosystem like a power system, the ontologies created under ontological realism guidance are well suited to act as the common models for most of the data sources in the part of the world the ontology in modeling as realist ontologies attempt to portray a portion of the world using as many everyday terminologies as possible. Despite being universal descriptions, data sources provide a layer of context to meet the demands of their stakeholders that are application-specific.

Adopting the ontological realism method also contributes to better governance. To be true to the realist approach, an ontology's assertions must be true of the world; if not, they must be corrected to be true. Using the world to evaluate the validity of an ontology provides a clear process for adjudicating disputes and continually improving the content of an ontology; this is a big advantage for long-term management (Rudnicki et al., 2016).

Figure 51: Summary of the ontology's entity classes, data, object properties, and relationships.

Furthermore, in the formation of ontology, the principle of single inheritance is used. According to this concept, in ontology, each entity class must be a subclass of precisely one other entity class, and anything belonging to a parent term also belongs to all child terms at lower levels. This means that each asserted taxonomy has a single root node and that each ontology has one or more asserted taxonomies as suitable components.

Keeping this background in mind, the HADGO is being developed using ontological realism as well as the single inheritance rules. The knowledge is derived from the hybrid AC/DC grid models in conjunction with expert judgments, and opinions from the involved experts.

5.2 Entity Classes

An introduction to top-level entity classes, as highlighted in Figure 52, is provided in this section. The classes include `hadgo:PowerGrid`, `hadgo:Component`,

Figure 52: Hierarchy of major asserted entity classes in HADGO.

hadgo:ComponentType, hadgo:FunctionType, hadgo:GridStateType, hadgo:PowerFlowType and hadgo:VoltageLevel. All of these entity classes are sub-classes of owl:Thing entity class, which is the default way of defining classes using the OWL. As in acOWL, everything is a sub-class of owl:Thing.

5.2.1 PowerGrid class

The `hadgo:PowerGrid` is the umbrella entity class that can represent an AC, DC, or hybrid grid. As shown in the class hierarchy in Figure 53, It is also one of the top-level classes and a direct sub-class of `owl:Thing`.

Figure 53: Hierarchy of the PowerGrid entity class.

The usage, relationships, object, and data properties for the `hadgo:PowerGrid` are summarized with the diagram shown in Figure 54. As can be seen, it has relations with most of the other high-level entity classes as the power grid is modeled using this class as the base. It can then include a number of `hadgo:Component` (and its specialized sub-classes like `hadgo:AcComponent` or `hadgo:DcComponent`). There are many functional and inverse object properties (see Appendix A) that help is adding more semantics to the relationship.

Figure 54: Overview of the PowerGrid and its sub-classes along with some properties and relationships.

5.2.2 Component class

The `hadgo:Component` is one of the major entity classes in the HADGO. Its class hierarchy is depicted in Figure 55. The `hadgo:Component` has two sub-classes for modeling an AC component `hadgo:AcComponent` and a DC component `hadgo:DcComponent`. Both AC and DC components are then divided into four sub-classes that distinguish them based on the type of function (`hadgo:FunctionType`) they are performing in the model. The asserted function

types, that a component can have are defined to be either `hadgo:Generation`, `hadgo:Storage`, `hadgo:Consumption`, or `hadgo:Transmission`.

Figure 55: Overview of the usage and relationships of the `hadgo:Component` Type and its sub-classes along with some properties and relationships.

Figure 56 shows the usage of the `hadgo:Component` entity class. As the figure shows, each component can have multiple object properties and relationships. One such relationship is with the `hadgo:ComponentType` entity class which helps in specifying the type of the specific instance of a component. A component can be either an `hadgo:AtomicComponent` or an `hadgo:ComponentComponent` meaning that the component consists of one than one component. The `hadgo:ComponentComponent` are specialized be of two kinds `hadgo:Transformer` and `hadgo:Converter`.

Furthermore, each `hadgo:Component` instance can have object properties that assign some `hadgo:GridStateType`. These `hadgo:GridStateType` can be either `hadgo:Dynamic` or `hadgo:Static` and represents `hadgo:Voltage`, `hadgo:Power` and `hadgo:Impedence`.

Each component instance must have a relationship with `hadgo:VoltageLevel` which defines, as the name suggests, the voltage level on which the component is operating. The asserted values as the range of object property are `hadgo:HighVoltage`, `hadgo:MediumVoltage`, and `hadgo:LowVoltage`.

5.2.3 ComponentType entity class

The `hadgo:ComponentType` entity class is defined to assert the types an `hadgo:Component` can have. Figure 57 depicts the class hierarchy. As can be seen in the figure, two specializations for this entity class are further defined as being `hadgo:AtomicComponent` and `hadgo:ComponentComponent`. The former covers the component instances that are atomic and usually have a single function, while the latter covers the component instances that can be composed of more than one component. The `hadgo:ComponentComponent` are further specialized with two sub-classes `hadgo:Converter` which represents an AC/DC converter as well as `hadgo:Transformer`.

Figure 56: Overview of the Component and its sub-classes along with some properties and relationships.

Figure 57: Class hierarchy for hadgo:ComponentType entity class.

Similarly, hadgo:AtomicComponent is specialized with two sub-classes that are hadgo:BusComponent and hadgo:LineComponent, which are self-explanatory. However, hadgo:BusComponent is further classified, as shown in Figure 58, into three specialized sub-classes hadgo:GeneratorBus, hadgo:LoadBus and hadgo:SlackBus.

Figure 58: Class hierarchy for the hadgo:BusComponent sub-class of hadgo:ComponentType entity class.

5.2.4 FunctionType class

The `hadgo:FunctionType` entity class defines the different types of function that a `hadgo:Component` can assume. The relationships and constraints are imposed using some object properties defining `hadgo:Component` as the domain and `hadgo:FunctionType` as the range. Figure 59 show the class hierarchy for this entity class. There are four specializations defined as the sub-classes that are `hadgo:Transmission`, `hadgo:Storage`, `hadgo:Generation`, `hadgo:Consumption`.

Figure 59: Class hierarchy for `hadgo:FunctionType` entity class.

5.2.5 GridStateType class

The entity class `hadgo:GridStateType` represents the measurable grid states that an instance of a component can have. Figure 60 shows the hierarchy for this entity class. As can be seen in the figure, there are two sub-classes defined as `hadgo:Static` and `hadgo:Dynamic`. The two sub-classes for the `hadgo:Dynamic` are `hadgo:Voltage` and `hadgo:Power` while `hadgo:Static` only has one that is `hadgo:Impedence`.

Figure 60: Class hierarchy for `hadgo:GridStateType` entity class.

5.2.6 PowerFlowType class

The entity class `hadgo:GridStateType` represents the power flows that an instance of a component in the grid can have. Changing this value affects the way this instance can be connected to other instances of the components and the type of object properties it can have. Figure 61

shows the hierarchy for this entity class. There are two specializations, `hadgo:AcPowerFlow` and `hadgo:DcPowerFlow` representing AC and DC power flow respectively.

Figure 61: Class hierarchy for `hadgo:PowerFlowType` entity class.

5.2.7 VoltageLevel class

The entity class `hadgo:VoltageLevel` represents the voltage level an instance of the `hadgo:Component` can have and it defines the voltage level on which the component is operating. As depicted in Figure 62, asserted sub-classes are `hadgo:HighVoltage`, `hadgo:MediumVoltage`, and `hadgo:LowVoltage`.

Figure 62: Class hierarchy for `hadgo:VoltageLevel` entity class.

5.2.8 UnitOfGridStateMeasure class

The entity class `hadgo:VoltageLevel` represents the units that are used for measuring `hadgo:GridStatType` that a `hadgo:Component` instance can have. As depicted in Figure 63, this entity class has children and grand-children that define first the phenomenon and then define the respective unit.

Figure 63: Class hierarchy for *hadgo:UnitOfGridStateMeasure* entity class.

6 Conclusions

The deliverable provides, first, detailed insight into various aspects and background on the development of an interoperable data model for the hybrid AC/DC grid in the HYPERRIDE project. Then HADGO ontology being developed for modeling and analyzing AC, DC, and hybrid power systems is introduced. The following outlines some of the insights:

- elaboration on the basic concepts such as interoperability, ontology, and data modeling;
- a details analysis of the state-of-the-art with a detailed description of the ten relevant open ontologies and vocabularies along with two data models;
- elaboration of the proposed methodology for the development of the ontology and the interoperable data model on top of it;
- introducing the hybrid AC DC Grid Ontology (HADGO).

Appendix A – HADGO Reference

This appendix serves as a reference on entity classes, axioms, data, and object properties for the HADGO ontology developed in the project and introduced in Section 5. Table 1 provides a list of symbols, their meaning, and a short explanation that can be used for reading the axioms. In this reference, first, entity classes are presented in alphabetical order and then the data and object properties are listed.

Symbol	Meaning	Explanation
\forall	(for all)	For All / Each (universal quantification)
\exists	(there exists/at least one)	There exists / at least one
\sqsubseteq	(subsumption)	Is a / is subsumed by
\equiv	(equivalence)	Is defined by
\sqcap	(and)	and (conjunction; DL notation)
\sqcup	(or)	or (disjunction; DL notation)
\neg	(not)	Not (logical negation)
\neq	(not equivalent)	Not equivalent
\perp	(bottom)	Empty set
\top	(top)	The domain
\in	(is member of)	Is member of
\geq	(greater than or equal to)	Minimum cardinality
\leq	(less than or equal to)	Maximum cardinality
\notin	(is not member of)	Is not a member of
\models	(entailment)	Entails models
\cup	(union)	Set union
\cap	(intersection)	Set intersection
\rightarrow	(implies)	Implies
\top	(top)	Top

Table 1: Symbols, meaning, and explanation for the interpretation of the asserted axioms.

Axioms for asserted classes

AcComponent

AcComponent \sqsubseteq Component

AcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ DcComponent

AcPowerFlow

AcPowerFlow \sqsubseteq PowerFlowType

AcPowerFlow $\sqsubseteq \neg$ DcPowerFlow

6.0.1 AngleUnit

AngleUnit \sqsubseteq UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 AngleUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ImpedenceUnit
 AngleUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ PowerUnit
 AngleUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ VoltageUnit
 AngleUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ImpedenceUnit
 PowerUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ImpedenceUnit
 VoltageUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ImpedenceUnit
 AngleUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ PowerUnit
 ImpedenceUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ PowerUnit
 VoltageUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ PowerUnit
 AngleUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ VoltageUnit
 ImpedenceUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ VoltageUnit
 PowerUnit $\sqsubseteq \neg$ VoltageUnit

AtomicComponent

AtomicComponent \sqsubseteq ComponentType
 AtomicComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ CompositComponent

BusComponent

BusComponent \sqsubseteq AtomicComponent
 BusComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ LineComponent

Component

Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType
 Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ FunctionType
 Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ GridStateType
 Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ PowerFlowType
 Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ PowerGrid
 Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ VoltageLevel
 Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType
 Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ FunctionType
 ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ FunctionType
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ FunctionType
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ FunctionType

PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel

ComponentType

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel

CompositComponent

CompositComponent \sqsubseteq ComponentType

CompositComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ AtomicComponent

Consumption

Consumption \sqsubseteq FunctionType

Consumption $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Generation

Consumption $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Storage

Consumption $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Transmission

Consumption $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Generation

Storage $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Generation

Transmission $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Generation

Consumption $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Storage

Generation $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Storage

Transmission $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Storage

Consumption $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Transmission

Generation $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Transmission

Storage $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Transmission

ConsumptionAcComponent

ConsumptionAcComponent \sqsubseteq AcComponent

ConsumptionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ GenerationAcComponent

ConsumptionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageAcComponent

ConsumptionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionAcComponent

ConsumptionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ GenerationAcComponent

StorageAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ GenerationAcComponent

TransmissionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ GenerationAcComponent

ConsumptionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageAcComponent

GenerationAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageAcComponent

TransmissionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageAcComponent

ConsumptionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionAcComponent

GenerationAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionAcComponent

StorageAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionAcComponent

ConsumptionDcComponent

ConsumptionDcComponent \sqsubseteq DcComponent

ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ GenerationDcComponent

ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageDcComponent

ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionDcComponent

ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ GenerationDcComponent

StorageDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ GenerationDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ GenerationDcComponent
 ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageDcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageDcComponent
 ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionDcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionDcComponent
 StorageDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionDcComponent

Converter

Converter \sqsubseteq CompositComponent

Converter $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Transformer

DcComponent

DcComponent \sqsubseteq Component

DcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ AcComponent

DcPowerFlow

DcPowerFlow \sqsubseteq PowerFlowType

DcPowerFlow $\sqsubseteq \neg$ AcPowerFlow

Dynamic

Dynamic \sqsubseteq GridStateType

Dynamic $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Static

FunctionType

ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Component

FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Component

GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Component

PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Component

PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Component

UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Component

VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Component

Component $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType

FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType

GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType

PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType

PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ComponentType

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel

Generation

Generation \sqsubseteq FunctionType

Generation \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Consumption

Storage $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Consumption
 Transmission $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Consumption
 Generation $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Consumption
 Generation $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Storage
 Generation $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Transmission
 Consumption $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Storage
 Generation $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Storage
 Transmission $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Storage
 Consumption $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Transmission
 Generation $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Transmission
 Storage $\sqsubseteq \neg$ Transmission

GenerationAcComponent

GenerationAcComponent \sqsubseteq AcComponent
 GenerationAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ConsumptionAcComponent
 StorageAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ConsumptionAcComponent
 TransmissionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ConsumptionAcComponent
 GenerationAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ConsumptionAcComponent
 GenerationAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageAcComponent
 GenerationAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionAcComponent
 ConsumptionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageAcComponent
 GenerationAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageAcComponent
 TransmissionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageAcComponent
 ConsumptionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionAcComponent
 GenerationAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionAcComponent
 StorageAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionAcComponent

GenerationDcComponent

GenerationDcComponent \sqsubseteq DcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ConsumptionDcComponent
 StorageDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ConsumptionDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ConsumptionDcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ ConsumptionDcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageDcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionDcComponent
 ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageDcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ StorageDcComponent
 ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionDcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionDcComponent
 StorageDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \neg$ TransmissionDcComponent

GeneratorBus

GeneratorBus \sqsubseteq BusComponent

GeneratorBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LoadBus

GeneratorBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow SlackBus

GeneratorBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LoadBus

SlackBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LoadBus

GeneratorBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow SlackBus

LoadBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow SlackBus

GridStateType

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel

Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType

FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType

PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType

Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel

HighVoltage

HighVoltage \sqsubseteq VoltageLevel
 HighVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LowVoltage
 HighVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow MediumVoltage
 HighVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LowVoltage
 MediumVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LowVoltage
 HighVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow MediumVoltage
 LowVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow MediumVoltage

Impedence

Impedence \sqsubseteq Static

ImpedenceUnit

ImpedenceUnit \sqsubseteq UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 ImpedenceUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow AngleUnit
 PowerUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow AngleUnit
 VoltageUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow AngleUnit
 ImpedenceUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow AngleUnit
 ImpedenceUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerUnit
 ImpedenceUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageUnit
 AngleUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerUnit

ImpedanceUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerUnit
VoltageUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerUnit
AngleUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageUnit
ImpedanceUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageUnit
PowerUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageUnit

LineComponent

LineComponent \sqsubseteq AtomicComponent
LineComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow BusComponent

LoadBus

LoadBus \sqsubseteq BusComponent
LoadBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GeneratorBus
SlackBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GeneratorBus
LoadBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GeneratorBus
LoadBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow SlackBus
GeneratorBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow SlackBus
LoadBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow SlackBus

LowVoltage

LowVoltage \sqsubseteq VoltageLevel
LowVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow HighVoltage
MediumVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow HighVoltage
LowVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow HighVoltage
LowVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow MediumVoltage
HighVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow MediumVoltage
LowVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow MediumVoltage

MediumVoltage

MediumVoltage \sqsubseteq VoltageLevel
LowVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow HighVoltage
MediumVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow HighVoltage
HighVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LowVoltage
MediumVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LowVoltage
MediumVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow HighVoltage
MediumVoltage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LowVoltage

Power

Power \sqsubseteq Dynamic

Power \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Voltage

PowerFlowType

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType

FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType

PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel

Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid

Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ VoltageLevel
 ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ VoltageLevel
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ VoltageLevel
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ VoltageLevel
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ VoltageLevel
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ VoltageLevel
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ VoltageLevel

PowerGrid

ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType
 ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType
 Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType
 ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType

GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel

PowerUnit

PowerUnit \sqsubseteq UnitOfGridStateMeasure

ImpedenceUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow AngleUnit
 PowerUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow AngleUnit
 VoltageUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow AngleUnit
 AngleUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ImpedenceUnit
 PowerUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ImpedenceUnit
 VoltageUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ImpedenceUnit
 PowerUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow AngleUnit
 PowerUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ImpedenceUnit
 PowerUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageUnit
 AngleUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageUnit
 ImpedenceUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageUnit
 PowerUnit \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageUnit

SlackBus

SlackBus \sqsubseteq BusComponent

LoadBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GeneratorBus

SlackBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GeneratorBus
 GeneratorBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LoadBus
 SlackBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LoadBus
 SlackBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GeneratorBus
 SlackBus \sqsubseteq \rightarrow LoadBus

Static

Static \sqsubseteq GridStateType
 Static \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Dynamic

Storage

Storage \sqsubseteq FunctionType
 Generation \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Consumption
 Storage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Consumption
 Transmission \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Consumption
 Consumption \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Generation
 Storage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Generation
 Transmission \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Generation
 Storage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Consumption
 Storage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Generation
 Storage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Transmission
 Consumption \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Transmission
 Generation \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Transmission
 Storage \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Transmission

StorageAcComponent

StorageAcComponent \sqsubseteq AcComponent
 GenerationAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ConsumptionAcComponent
 StorageAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ConsumptionAcComponent
 TransmissionAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ConsumptionAcComponent
 ConsumptionAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GenerationAcComponent
 StorageAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GenerationAcComponent
 TransmissionAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GenerationAcComponent
 StorageAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ConsumptionAcComponent
 StorageAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GenerationAcComponent
 StorageAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow TransmissionAcComponent
 ConsumptionAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow TransmissionAcComponent
 GenerationAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow TransmissionAcComponent
 StorageAcComponent \sqsubseteq \rightarrow TransmissionAcComponent

StorageDcComponent

StorageDcComponent \sqsubseteq DcComponent

GenerationDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg ConsumptionDcComponent

StorageDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg ConsumptionDcComponent

TransmissionDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg ConsumptionDcComponent

ConsumptionDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg GenerationDcComponent

StorageDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg GenerationDcComponent

TransmissionDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg GenerationDcComponent

StorageDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg ConsumptionDcComponent

StorageDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg GenerationDcComponent

StorageDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg TransmissionDcComponent

ConsumptionDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg TransmissionDcComponent

GenerationDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg TransmissionDcComponent

StorageDcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg TransmissionDcComponent

Transformer

Transformer \sqsubseteq CompositComponent

Transformer \sqsubseteq \neg Converter

Transmission

Transmission \sqsubseteq FunctionType

Generation \sqsubseteq \neg Consumption

Storage \sqsubseteq \neg Consumption

Transmission \sqsubseteq \neg Consumption

Consumption \sqsubseteq \neg Generation

Storage \sqsubseteq \neg Generation

Transmission \sqsubseteq \neg Generation

Consumption \sqsubseteq \neg Storage

Generation \sqsubseteq \neg Storage

Transmission \sqsubseteq \neg Storage

Transmission \sqsubseteq \neg Consumption

Transmission \sqsubseteq \neg Generation

Transmission \sqsubseteq \neg Storage

TransmissionAcComponent

TransmissionAcComponent \sqsubseteq AcComponent

GenerationAcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg ConsumptionAcComponent

StorageAcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg ConsumptionAcComponent

TransmissionAcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg ConsumptionAcComponent

ConsumptionAcComponent \sqsubseteq \neg GenerationAcComponent

StorageAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GenerationAcComponent
 TransmissionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GenerationAcComponent
 ConsumptionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ StorageAcComponent
 GenerationAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ StorageAcComponent
 TransmissionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ StorageAcComponent
 TransmissionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ConsumptionAcComponent
 TransmissionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GenerationAcComponent
 TransmissionAcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ StorageAcComponent

TransmissionDcComponent

TransmissionDcComponent \sqsubseteq DcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ConsumptionDcComponent
 StorageDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ConsumptionDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ConsumptionDcComponent
 ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GenerationDcComponent
 StorageDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GenerationDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GenerationDcComponent
 ConsumptionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ StorageDcComponent
 GenerationDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ StorageDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ StorageDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ConsumptionDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GenerationDcComponent
 TransmissionDcComponent $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ StorageDcComponent

UnitOfGridStateMeasure

ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 VoltageLevel \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow Component
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow ComponentType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow FunctionType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow GridStateType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerFlowType
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow PowerGrid
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 Component \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 ComponentType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 FunctionType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 GridStateType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerFlowType \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 PowerGrid \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel
 UnitOfGridStateMeasure \sqsubseteq \rightarrow VoltageLevel

V

V \sqsubseteq VoltageUnit

VAr

VAr \sqsubseteq PowerUnit

VAr \sqsubseteq \rightarrow W

Voltage

Voltage \sqsubseteq Dynamic

Voltage $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Power

VoltageLevel

ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component

FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component

GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component

PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component

PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component

UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component

VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component

Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType

FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType

GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType

PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType

PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType

VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType

Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType

ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType

GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType

PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType

PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType

VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType

Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType

ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType

FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType

PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType

PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType

VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType

Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType

ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType

FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType

GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType

PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType

UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType

VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType

Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerGrid

ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerGrid

FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerGrid

GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerGrid

PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerGrid

UnitOfGridStateMeasure $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerGrid

VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerGrid

Component $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 ComponentType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 FunctionType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 GridStateType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerFlowType $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 PowerGrid $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ Component
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ComponentType
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ FunctionType
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ GridStateType
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerFlowType
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerGrid
 VoltageLevel $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ UnitOfGridStateMeasure

VoltageUnit

VoltageUnit \sqsubseteq UnitOfGridStateMeasure

ImpedenceUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ AngleUnit
 PowerUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ AngleUnit
 VoltageUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ AngleUnit
 AngleUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ImpedenceUnit
 PowerUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ImpedenceUnit
 VoltageUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ImpedenceUnit
 AngleUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerUnit
 ImpedenceUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerUnit
 VoltageUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerUnit
 VoltageUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ AngleUnit
 VoltageUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ ImpedenceUnit
 VoltageUnit $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ PowerUnit

W

W \sqsubseteq PowerUnit

W $\sqsubseteq \rightarrow$ VAR

deg

deg \sqsubseteq AngleUnit

r

r \sqsubseteq ImpedenceUnit

Object properties

hasComponent

\sqsubseteq topObjectProperty

hasComponent \equiv isPowerGrid⁻

\exists hasComponent Thing \sqsubseteq PowerGrid

$\top \sqsubseteq \forall$ hasComponent Component

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
 State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
 ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasConnectionTo

\sqsubseteq topObjectProperty

hasConnectionTo \equiv isConnectedTo⁻

\exists hasConnectionTo Thing \sqsubseteq Component

$\top \sqsubseteq \forall$ hasConnectionTo Component

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
 State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
 ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasFunction

\sqsubseteq topObjectProperty

\exists hasFunction Thing \sqsubseteq Component

$\top \sqsubseteq \forall$ hasFunction FunctionType

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
 State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
 ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasGridState

\sqsubseteq topObjectProperty

\exists hasGridState Thing \sqsubseteq Component

$\top \sqsubseteq \forall$ hasGridState GridStateType

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
 State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
 ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasImpedanceUnit

⊆ topObjectProperty

∃ hasImpedanceUnit Thing ⊆ Impedance

⊤ ⊆ ∇ hasImpedanceUnit r

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
 State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
 ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasPowerFlowTyp

⊆ topObjectProperty

⊤ ⊆ ≤ 1 hasPowerFlowTyp Thing

∃ hasPowerFlowTyp Thing ⊆ Component

⊤ ⊆ ∇ hasPowerFlowTyp PowerFlowType

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
 State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
 ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasPowerUnit

⊆ topObjectProperty

∃ hasPowerUnit Thing ⊆ Power

⊤ ⊆ ∇ hasPowerUnit PowerUnit

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
 State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
 ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasType

⊆ topObjectProperty

∃ hasType Thing ⊆ Component

⊤ ⊆ ∇ hasType ComponentType

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
 State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
 ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasUnit

⊆ topObjectProperty

\exists hasUnit Thing \sqsubseteq GridStateType

$\top \sqsubseteq \forall$ hasUnit UnitOfGridStateMeasure

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasVoltageLevel

\sqsubseteq topObjectProperty

$\top \sqsubseteq \leq 1$ hasVoltageLevel Thing

\exists hasVoltageLevel Thing \sqsubseteq Component

$\top \sqsubseteq \forall$ hasVoltageLevel VoltageLevel

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

hasVoltageUnit

\sqsubseteq topObjectProperty

\exists hasVoltageUnit Thing \sqsubseteq Voltage

$\top \sqsubseteq \forall$ hasVoltageUnit V

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

isConnectedTo

\sqsubseteq topObjectProperty

hasConnectionTo \equiv isConnectedTo⁻

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

isPowerGrid

\sqsubseteq topObjectProperty

hasComponent \equiv isPowerGrid⁻

DisjointObjectProperties hasComponent hasConnectionTo hasFunction hasGrid-
State hasImpedanceUnit hasPowerFlowTyp hasPowerUnit hasType hasUnit hasVolt-
ageLevel hasVoltageUnit isConnectedTo isPowerGrid

topObjectProperty

Data properties

hasActivePowerValue

⊆ topDataProperty

∃ hasActivePowerValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#Literal ⊆ Power

⊆ ⊆ ∇ hasActivePowerValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#real

hasActivePowerValue ≠ hasReactanceValue ≠ hasReactivePowerValue ≠ hasResistanceValue ≠ hasVolatageAngleValue ≠ hasVoltageMagnitudeValue

hasReactanceValue

⊆ topDataProperty

∃ hasReactanceValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#Literal ⊆ Impedence

⊆ ⊆ ∇ hasReactanceValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#real

hasActivePowerValue ≠ hasReactanceValue ≠ hasReactivePowerValue ≠ hasResistanceValue ≠ hasVolatageAngleValue ≠ hasVoltageMagnitudeValue

hasReactivePowerValue

⊆ topDataProperty

∃ hasReactivePowerValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#Literal ⊆ Power

⊆ ⊆ ∇ hasReactivePowerValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#real

hasActivePowerValue ≠ hasReactanceValue ≠ hasReactivePowerValue ≠ hasResistanceValue ≠ hasVolatageAngleValue ≠ hasVoltageMagnitudeValue

hasResistanceValue

⊆ topDataProperty

∃ hasResistanceValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#Literal ⊆ Impedence

⊆ ⊆ ∇ hasResistanceValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#real

hasActivePowerValue ≠ hasReactanceValue ≠ hasReactivePowerValue ≠ hasResistanceValue ≠ hasVolatageAngleValue ≠ hasVoltageMagnitudeValue

hasVolatageAngleValue

□ topDataProperty

∃ hasVolatageAngleValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#Literal □ Voltage

⊔ □ ∀ hasVolatageAngleValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#real

hasActivePowerValue ≠ hasReactanceValue ≠ hasReactivePowerValue ≠ hasResistanceValue ≠ hasVolatageAngleValue ≠ hasVoltageMagnitudeValue

hasVoltageMagnitudeValue

□ topDataProperty

∃ hasVoltageMagnitudeValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#Literal □ Voltage

⊔ □ ∀ hasVoltageMagnitudeValue Datatypehttp://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#real

hasActivePowerValue ≠ hasReactanceValue ≠ hasReactivePowerValue ≠ hasResistanceValue ≠ hasVolatageAngleValue ≠ hasVoltageMagnitudeValue

References

- Alfaifi, Y. (2022). Ontology development methodology: A systematic review and case study. In *2022 2nd international conference on computing and information technology (iccit)* (p. 446-450). doi: 10.1109/ICCIT52419.2022.9711664
- Ariza, J., Larrinaga, F., & Curry, E. (2020, 01). Dabgeo: A reusable and usable global energy ontology for the energy domain. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3531214
- Booshehri, M., Emele, L., Flügel, S., Förster, H., Frey, J., Frey, U., ... Stappel, M. (2021). Introducing the open energy ontology: Enhancing data interpretation and interfacing in energy systems analysis. *Energy and AI*, 5, 100074 -. Retrieved from <https://juser.fz-juelich.de/record/894340> doi: 10.1016/j.egyai.2021.100074
- Bruinenberg, J., Colton, L., Darmois, E., Dorn, J., Doyle, J., Elloumi, O., ... Uslar, M. (2012). *Cen -cenelec - etsi: Smart grid coordination group - smart grid reference architecture report 2.0*.
- Costin, A. M., Eastman, C., & Issa, R. R. A. (2017). The need for taxonomies in the ontological approach for interoperability of heterogeneous information models. In *Computing in civil engineering 2017* (p. 9-17). Retrieved from <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/9780784480830.002> doi: 10.1061/9780784480830.002
- Cuenca, J. (2018a). *Oema energy and equipment ontology*. Retrieved from <https://innoweb.mondragon.edu/ontologies/oema/enaq/1.1/index-en.html>
- Cuenca, J. (2018b). *Oema ontology network*. Retrieved from <https://innoweb.mondragon.edu/ontologies/oema/ontologynetwork/1.1/index-en.htm>
- Cuenca, J., Larrinaga, F., & Curry, E. (2017). A unified semantic ontology for energy management applications. In *Wsp/womocoe@iswc*.
- Dabgeo: Domain analysis-based global energy ontology*. (2019). Retrieved from <https://innoweb.mondragon.edu/ontologies/dabgeo/index-en.html>
- Devanand, A., Karmakar, G., Krdzavac, N., Rigo-Mariani, R., Eddy, Y., Karimi, I., & Kraft, M. (2020, 05). Ontopowsys: A power system ontology for cross domain interactions in an eco industrial park. *Energy and AI*, 1, 100008. doi: 10.1016/j.egyai.2020.100008
- ETSI. (2017). *Etsi ts 103 410-1 v1.1.1 smartm2m; smart appliances extension to saref; part 1: Energy domain*. Retrieved from https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/103400_103499/10341001/01.01.01_60/ts_10341001v010101p.pdf
- ETSI. (2020a). *Saref4ener: an extension of saref for the energy domain created in collaboration with energy@home and eebus associations*. Retrieved from <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4ener/v1.1.2/>
- ETSI. (2020b). *Saref: the smart applications reference ontology*. Retrieved from <https://saref.etsi.org/core/v3.1.1/>
- Gopstein, A., Nguyen, C., adn N. Hastings, C. O., & Wollman, D. (2021). *Nist special publication 1108r4 - nist framework and roadmap for smart grid interoperability standards, release 4.0*. Retrieved from <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/NIST.SP.1108r4.pdf>

- GS, E. (2020). *Etsi gs cim 009 v1.2.2 context information management (cim); ngsi-ld api*. Retrieved from https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/CIM/001_099/009/01.02.02_60/gc_CIM009v010202p.pdf
- Haas, L. M., Lin, E. T., & Roth, M. A. (2002, oct). Data integration through database federation. *IBM Syst. J.*, 41(4), 578–596. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1147/sj.414.0578> doi: 10.1147/sj.414.0578
- Haghighi, M., Sychev, I., & Monti, A. (2020, 10). Sargon – smart energy domain ontology. *Smart Cities*. doi: 10.1049/iet-smc.2020.0049
- Hargreaves, N., Pantea, S., & Taylor, G. (2014, 01). Adopting the IEC common information model to enable smart grid interoperability and knowledge representation processes. *Green Energy and Technology*, 439-462. doi: 10.1007/978-981-4585-30-9_17
- Hutschenreuter, H., Çakmakçı, S. D., Maeder, C., & Kemmerich, T. (2021). Ontology-based cybersecurity and resilience framework. In P. Mori, G. Lenzini, & S. Furnell (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 7th international conference on information systems security and privacy, icissp 2021, online streaming, february 11-13, 2021* (p. 458-466). SCITEPRESS. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5220/0010233604580466> doi: 10.5220/0010233604580466
- HYPERRIDE Description of Action*. (2020). HYPERRIDE Consortium.
- IEEE standard glossary of software engineering terminology. (1990). *IEEE Std 610.12-1990*, 1-84. doi: 10.1109/IEEESTD.1990.101064
- ITU-T. (1994). *X.200 : Information technology - open systems interconnection - basic reference model: The basic model*. Retrieved from <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X.200-199407-I>
- Jang, J.-H., Hussain, A., Seo, J.-S., Kim, H.-S., Seok, C.-J., Kim, T.-W., ... Lee, S.-J. (2013, 10). Study on method of integrating the existing system with CIM-based system..
- Klaver, M., Luijck, E., Nieuwenhuijs, A., Os, N., & Oskam, V. (2015, 10). Critical infrastructure assessment by emergency management.. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-33331-1_7
- Lauretis, L. D., Costantini, S., & Letteri, I. (2019). An ontology to improve the first aid service quality. In *2019 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics (SMC)* (p. 1479-1483). doi: 10.1109/SMC.2019.8914460
- Lefrançois, M. (2017, July). Planned ETSI SAREF Extensions based on the W3C&OGC SOSA/SSN-compatible SEAS Ontology Patterns. In *Proceedings of workshop on semantic interoperability and standardization in the iot, sis-iot*..
- Lefrançois, M., Kalaoja, J., Ghariani, T., & Zimmermann, A. (2016). *SEAS Knowledge Model* (Deliverable No. 2.2). ITEA2 12004 Smart Energy Aware Systems. (76 p.)
- Li, T., Zhao, Y., Zhang, C., Zhou, K., & Zhang, X. (2022). A semantic model-based fault detection approach for building energy systems. *Building and Environment*, 207, 108548. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360132321009410> doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2021.108548>
- Narayanan, S., Maruchek, A., & Handfield, R. (2009, 02). Electronic data interchange: Research review and future directions*. *Decision Sciences*, 40, 121 - 163. doi: 10.1111/j.1540-5915.2008.00218.x

- opendigitaltwins-energygrid github repository*. (2021). Retrieved from <https://github.com/Azure/opendigitaltwins-energygrid/>
- Open energy platform ontology github repository*. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/ontology>
- Paolucci, M., & Souville, B. (2012, 05). Data interoperability in the future of middleware. *Journal of Internet Services and Applications*, 3. doi: 10.1007/s13174-012-0059-x
- R. Arp, A. S., B. Smith. (2015). *Building ontologies with basic formal ontology*. doi: 10.7551/mitpress/9780262527811.001.0001
- Rudnicki, R., Smith, B., Malyuta, T., & Mandrick, W. (2016, oct 25). *White Paper: Best Practices of Ontology Development*. https://www.nist.gov/system/files/documents/2021/10/14/nist-ai-rfi-cubrc_inc_002.pdf. ([Online; accessed 2023-04-24])
- Salameh, K., Chbeir, R., Camblong, H., Tekli, G., & Vechiu, I. (2015, 09). A generic ontology-based information model for better management of microgrids. In (Vol. 458). doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-23868-5_33.Oral
- SAMIRMI, F., Tang, W., & WU, Q. (2015, 11). Fuzzy ontology reasoning for power transformer fault diagnosis. *Advances in Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 15, 107-114. doi: 10.4316/AECE.2015.04015
- Santoro, F., Mira da Silva, M., Fernandes, A., & Toscano, B. (2022, 01). A domain ontology on cascading effects in critical infrastructures based on a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Critical Infrastructures*, 18, 1. doi: 10.1504/IJCIS.2022.10044304
- Smith, B., & Ceusters, W. (2010). Ontological realism: A methodology for coordinated evolution of scientific ontologies. *Appl Ontol.*, 5(3-4), 139-188. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3104413/>. doi: 10.3233/AO-2010-0079
- Smith, B., Ceusters, W., Klagges, B., Köhler, J., Kumar, A., Lomax, J., ... Rosse, C. (2005, 02). Relations in biomedical ontologies. *Genome biology*, 6, R46. doi: 10.1186/gb-2005-6-5-r46
- Spyns, P., Meersman, R., & Jarrar, M. (2002, 03). Data modelling versus ontology engineering. *ACM SIGMOD Record*, 31, 12-17. doi: 10.1145/637411.637413
- Uslar, M., Offis, T. S., Information, B., Management, K., Lucks, A., & Luhmann, T. (n.d.). *Interaction of EMS related systems by using the CIM standard*.
- W3C. (2004a). *W3c recommendation owl web ontology language overview*. Retrieved from <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-features/>
- W3C. (2004b). *W3c recommendation resource description framework (rdf): Concepts and abstract syntax*. Retrieved from <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-concepts/>
- W3C. (2008). *W3c recommendation extensible markup language (xml) 1.0 (fifth edition)*. Retrieved from <https://www.w3.org/TR/xml/>
- W3C. (2014). *Resource description framework (rdf)*. Retrieved from <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>
- Widergren, S., Hardin, D., Ambrosio, R., Drummond, R., Gunther, E., Gilchrist, G., & Cohen, D. (2008, 01). Gridwise interoperability context-setting framework.

Wikipedia. (n.d.). *Data model*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_model

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